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**The Shape of *Biomutant*: a Comparative Study About
Narrative and Linguistic Choices in Game Localization**

Relatore:

Ch.mo Prof. Pietro Luigi IAIA

Correlatore:

Ch.mo Prof. Thomas, Wulstan CHRISTIANSEN

Laureando:

Graziano Ferilli

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*A Tommaso, mio padre, per l'amore paterno e l'ascolto.
A Genna, la mia stella, per i sorrisi e le coccole.
A Martina, la mia forza, per la tenacia, l'amore per la vita.*

*A chi c'è stato e non c'è più.
A chi c'è ancora.
A chi ci sarà.*

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Introduction

This thesis is a labor of love that took almost a year to be conceived. It all started in November 2024, when I got the chance to play and experience *Biomutant* for fun for the first time. While playing, I noticed a plethora of interesting Italian localizations that I felt had to be academically discussed at some point in time. Since then, the idea to find a right frame for this thesis has been the first priority. Soon enough, the first questions I had about this game started popping up in my mind. “How was this localized and why?” “Why is ‘Surf’ localized as ‘Spuma’?” and “How on earth should ‘Scalo-Ciuf’ be in English?” are just a small glimpse of what was going on into my mind back then.

First ideas became the blueprint for a route, something that had yet to be paved in my mind. With each month passing, more and more elements got added and the road became clearer and clearer by the minute. In due time, *Biomutant* has become a conductor that guides readers through all of its nuances and facets, going from stepping stone to stepping stone and leaving ample room for a comparative study among other video games.

The first chapter (also known as “zone”) is completely dedicated to theoretical elements. Starting off with the question “why?”, it explains why *Biomutant* got chosen as the perfect guide through the whole study, as well as its history and all of the elements that this thesis will need, starting from what is generically defined as Translation, as well as some of its methods, then moving along to Audio Visual Translation, a quick glimpse of what is narrativity in the video games media and a look at some embryonic linguistic rules in newborn languages. Furthermore, there is a look at what are the

definitions for Game Localization and Transcreation, as well as a quick look at the state of the former in 2025.

The second zone is completely dedicated to Translational studies. With *Biomutant* being the focus case, every element that characterizes it will be taken into account, such as its linguistic rules, some differences between English and Italian Localizations and its actual narrativity, which will be put besides another, similarly narrated game, *Stories: The Path of Destinies*, as a comparison. This comparison then shifts towards wordplay and composite phrases, with *Biomutant* being put besides the first two *Splatoon* games in order to see how much they differ in jokes and wordplays.

The third zone is a follow-up of the second one, still exploring all of the facets of Translation with a simple question: what happens if and when a Localization cannot convey the same meanings of the original text? Transcreation comes to help. With *Biomutant* being set aside for this Zone, but also taken into account with a few Transcreation examples, everything in this Zone is dedicated to four main cases of Transcreation that have been chosen in different moments of video game history. The first three cases related to *Medieval*, *Super Paper Mario* and *Spyro: Year of the Dragon*, as well as their remakes, reboots and remasters, focus on how Transcreation can also be related to diatopic variations, especially if the original characters have a thick accent that should be addressed in the process. The fourth case related to *Rayman 3: Hoodlum Havoc*, is quite special. With this localization happening from French, this is the only part of the thesis that observes how Transcreation happened between the French and the English version, with the Italian one exploring the other possibilities of Translation that have been chosen by their localizers.

The fourth and final zone is dedicated to the discussion. It observes the reasons behind why other games have been chosen and how they fit the bill

in spite of others, as well as how the video game landscape changed after *Biomutant* came out, both as a video game and as a Localization example. The Localization studios of the games taken into this study are observed in order to also understand the work conditions and experiences for each game.

Finally, the questions that inform the study that is illustrated in this thesis are:

- How has *Biomutant* been localized? What are its strengths and weaknesses?
- Are all games like this? Are their structures common in the media?
- Which ones are the most similar to *Biomutant*? Do they work the same way?
- What happens if Translation is not enough? When is Transcreation used?
- What do professionals think about Transcreation?
- What is the background of the games that have been explored?
- What is to be expected in regards of how Localization is tackled after *Biomutant*?

Zone 1: simply put

1-1 - The case study: “*Biomutant*” (2021). Why this game?

Contents and Context

Starting this thesis is no easy task. There are a lot of things to think about, all coming from many different academic areas. In order to set things straight, a clear definition of the main case study of this thesis has to happen even before its elements are set out and explained as simply as possible.

Biomutant is the case study of this thesis. It is an Action Role-Playing Game (ARPG) set in a post-apocalyptic reality in which You, the player, create your own character, shape it however you want and then explore this vast world in order to save it from impending and (most likely) inevitable doom. The idea for the game started around 2015 from Swedish studio Experiment 101, established by former Avalance Studio¹ developers (the same people that worked on the *Just Cause* Series). With only 20 people to count on in 2018, development of *Biomutant* started off modest.

As history tells us today, *Biomutant* came out almost four years after its official announcement in 2017. 2021 saw *Biomutant* coming out to a mixed set of reviews, mostly around 6 out of 10 for most journalists, averaging around a maximum of 80/100 for Xbox Series X|S players.² It could be really easy to define this game as unremarkable, but this thesis was born because its way of communicating to the player is rather unique. It has a specific set of linguistic rules, localizations and general ideas that are not common in the vast panorama of the video games media. Despite not being a stellar

¹ <https://www.experiment101.com>.

² <https://www.metacritic.com/game/biomutant/>.

experience for most players, *Biomutant* has managed to pique my interest thanks to its unique ways to narrate itself, just like a fairy tale set in ancient Asia.

1-2 - A generic definition of Translation and its methods

Before getting to the core of the matter, it is mandatory to set some fundamental ground rules that will be of great importance later down the line. All the work around game localization and adaptation that will be explored in this thesis could not have existed if the basis of the communication process was not to understand each other's words, be it if the similarities between languages are close or far. Translation as a study took on many different shapes and sizes. For example, as Newmark (1991) originally put it, important texts need to be translated as closely as possible to their original meaning. This is one of the many starting points that still stand today in some shape or form. For something to be close to its original counterpart is the quintessential element of translation. This is not a law, but a guideline that helps translators deciding if and when to be more creative, or to be as close as possible to the original idea of what has been written or told.

Translators can, in fact, play, be creative and be free within set boundaries that are usually dictated by the clients that are asking for the translation or by the translators themselves. The idea of creativity is the jump-start for a lot of branches of translations that set aside the truthfully rigid ideas of being as close as possible to a word-for-word transposition of a text. Some things, be it meanings or significances, are bound to be lost in translation, so it is vital for a translator to adapt and to decide if and when to tap the creativity faucet and start finding similarities that can overcome these issues.

These similarities, or rather, interpretations, can shape up to be real challenges that have always been a subject of discussions. Signs, as they are called, can vastly differ from one another, so it is up to the translators or localizers to understand what is the best course of action. All verbal signs, be it texts or simple speech acts, can be translated in many different ways. In this case, Jakobson (1959) defines three kinds of translations:

- **Intralingual/rewording:** verbal signs are interpreted by means of other signs of the same language
- **Interlingual/Translation proper:** verbal signs are interpreted by the means of another language
- **Intersemiotic/Transmutation:** Verbal signs are interpreted by means of signs of nonverbal sign systems.

These three processes are the basis behind the whole translation act, making it an extremely versatile starting point. It is important to note that Jakobson understood from the beginning that finding a balance of equivalence is the main problem of language and the pivotal concern of linguistics. Catching the meaning of something by putting something else that has an equivalent effect will always be the best way to make a translation work when there are no exact words to choose from. It becomes worth noting at this point that the concepts of Domestication and Foreignization introduced by Lawrence Venuti (1995) make way for a better understanding of the translation of a text depending on its context:

- **Domestication** is a type of adaptation to the target culture. This type of strategy makes way for a total reduction of alterations of language and culture, trying to make the text as transparent as possible.
- **Foreignization** tries to maintain the cultural differences that the original text contains, focusing on how weird it might seem for the people on the receiving end.

Another point worth mentioning is related to the translation process that have been recognized as integral parts of Translation Theory. Here are the main ones:

- **Omission:** something is “forgotten” for clarity purposes
- **Addition:** Something is added in order to better explain a concept
- **Neutralization:** Some ideological or cultural traits are deleted or reduced to make the text more neutral and universal
- **Compensation:** A linguistic or stylistic effect that is lost at some point in a text that gets translated later on
- **Modulation:** Conceptual variation of a meaning
- **Transposition:** Grammatical category changes while keeping the same sense.
- **Equivalence:** The same pragmatical or idiomatic effect is produced with different linguistic methods
- **Adaptation:** A culturally diverse element of the source culture is substituted with something analogical in the target culture.
- **Generalization:** When a generic term is used instead of the original, mainly because there are no specific correspondents.
- **Particularization (or Specification):** Usage of a more specific term to clarify a vague definition or avoid polysemy.

A “TT” (Target Text) will be deemed as acceptable when its “ST” (Source Text) will be transposed as faithfully as possible. Then again, it is important to note that only the original text can fully contain everything the author(s) has to say in its original form. Translators have to be faithful to what has been originally written while keeping a fair degree of interpretation where needed. Things have rapidly been changing these past few years, especially in regards of consumable media products, such as movies, books or video games.

1-3 - Audio Visual Translation (AVT): The What, The How and The Why

The conjunction point between Translation and Game Localization can certainly be found in Audio Visual Translation (henceforth, AVT), which is the umbrella term that defines all types of translations that are dedicated to audiovisual products. AVT is composed of three main categories:

1. **Dubbing:** when the original audio track of, for example, a movie, is switched with another one that has voices in another language
2. **Voice-Over:** a more economical approach to dubbing in which the original audio is lowered, not switched, while the TT language is put at a higher volume in the same scene, resulting in two audio tracks at the same time.
3. **Subtitling:** a written form of translation that puts the TT language on-screen matching the timings of the original audio track.³
4. **Other types of subtitling and dubbing:** fan-subbing and fan-dubbing (non-official translations made by fans of a particular product, both in subtitling and dubbing forms), User-Generated Translations (subtitles made by amateurs, but officially made in accord with the companies or creators), Subtitles for the Hard of Hearing (which can contain extra captions and definitions or be longer in its timings).⁴

AVT is a mandatory step in order to understand the whole process that stands at the basis of game localization and similar types of adaptations. Some, like Remael (2010), still define it as a limited form of translation, be it textually or audio-wise, but it is a kind of translation process that keeps on changing

³ J.C. Díaz, *Audiovisual Translation in the Third Millennium*, 2003, p.195.

⁴ A. Remael, *Audiovisual Translation*, 2010, p.12.

and shifting as time goes on, depending on the needs and on the evolution of technology.

1-4 - Narrativity in the video games media

In order to move on to Game Localization there is the need of a slight detour from the translation process. The whole point of translating an audio-visual product is to transpose a story, its deeper meanings and small nuances. Because of this, it is fundamental to set a piece from another puzzle to understand videogames and their narrativity. Narration and communication go hand in hand, for Elleström (2019). To narrate is to communicate something, sharing ideas, notions and thoughts, putting what's in the mind of the author out in the open for the world to see, hear, feel and think.

Our focus is mainly related to simpler, more plot-driven narratives that leave nothing to randomness. Those plots that do not move because of inertia, but are specifically bound to a set number of events in a specific amount of time. Also defined as fairy tales, their purpose is to celebrate the marks of humanity as magically as possible, with the precise intent to end happily and leave a lasting impression and a morale that becomes impactful thanks to the events of the story.

What matters most in a fairy tale is the main character. They will be the ones that will confront against a villain, and have to win a lot of battles and tests in order to overcome their weaknesses and fears and give closure to their own destinies. Mysteries, strong items, magic itself, are all part of the process that makes a story impactful. The most important part of it is its formulaic structure that has rarely changed in time. This is maybe the most important element to set before moving on, because the case study of this thesis contains

a narrative arc that has radically been positioned in a “fairy tale” state from which it cannot be divided, despite not having the best of endings.

What is most peculiar about *Biomutant* is how closely it resembles a fairy tale in all its parts: You, the protagonist, are the chosen one that will inevitably fight against the main antagonist of the story, the one that destroyed your childhood and is a current menace against the whole society. “McGuffins”, as Hitchcock (1967) calls it, are what sets the plot of *Biomutant* in motion and make it endearing for the whole duration of its story. If the game plays its cards right, the player will eventually be invested in the plot of their own character and try to see it through, mainly thanks to how the narrator of the game explains whatever is happening on screen at all times in a language the player can easily understand, while at the same time all characters will communicate using a fictitious language composed of grunts and cries.

Speaking about the concept of moral, another key element at the start of the game is environmentalism, which also explains how humanity went extinct and how these mutant anthropomorphic creatures came to be, despite not being next in line in the evolutionary process. All of this is conveyed through the narrator whenever the player stops and tries to interact with promotional art from the “Old World”. Everything in the game is remembered, recounted and explained by the narrator. This entity does not take a specific shape (despite being sometimes superimposed over a mysterious figure in the game that takes the name of “mirage” and gifts the player old skills they forgot or memories they suppressed), but it is fundamental in order to give a specific rhythm to the game.

1-5 - Linguistic Rules in newborn languages

As has already been mentioned, *Biomutant* is a post-apocalyptic video game set in a world where its characters do not actually speak a real language. This new reality is completely made up, but the world in which these creatures live is most likely similar to ours, warts and all. With the reality of *Biomutant* being similar in spirit to that of a new society forming and shaping itself into a new version of its former, it would be safe to assume that many of the communication processes have the same rules of the real world, despite being confined in a video game. There are some examples that make this definition true, or at least spark some interest in how words have been written in the video game itself, but these will be explored later.

First off, let us assume that the linguistic reality in *Biomutant* starts from anthropomorphic animals that slowly and steadily get a grasp of how the “Old World” languages used to be spoken. It is also safe to assume that, at the point that the game starts, there is a fairly advanced degree of understanding of the languages, making the reality of the videogame really close to how languages used to shape up in our real world. As linguists like Graffi and Scalise (2002) put it, there could have been a point in time in which discrete but primitive sounds and grunts uttered by humans expressed emotions without having a symbolic value and then, in due time, started shaping up into actual words and utterances. This could be related to the growth in weight of the human brain that actually happened at some point in time.

With the possibility of a similar evolution being in the reality of *Biomutant*, it would also be safe to assume that the most literate of animals started understanding human language, eventually shaping it however they like. An important rule to set and remember to back up this idea would be reduplication, a real morphological process that consists in duplicating a word

segment in order to enforce its meaning or definition. It can either be partial or total, depending on the language. There are some words and definitions in the specific case of the video game *Biomutant* that do make large use of this morphological ruleset, despite not being verbal, but nominal in nature.

The Reduplication rule, as well as many other actual definitions that stem from the previous world or from onomatopoeias, make the idea of a realistic linguistic growth in *Biomutant* really plausible.

1-6 - Getting to the point: Game Localization and Transcreation

Getting back on the track of translation studies, it is time to discuss Game Localization, which intersects with many elements of AVT, like Du and Liu (2025) assert. Game Localization is not as simple as translating a text, as it refers to translating a completely interactive experience. It is a functional form of translation intended to deliver a gameplay experience in the Target Language that can be comparable to the original one, always keeping in mind that the Target Culture may occasionally prevail over the Source Culture depending on the cultural influences a video game may show through its contents. This is why, as already stated by Mangiron and O’ Hagan (2006), localizers are granted greater levels of freedom in order to convey the same message and meanings.

Game Localization can be defined as “the process of translation and adapting of a video game to attract a plethora of players surpassing linguistic barriers as well as cultures, geopolitical states and regions with conflicting politics and laws”. Yet, it just cannot be oversimplified this much, as O’Hagan and Mangiron (2018) state. It is also important to remember that game

localization needs a different kind of care put into it, something that depends not only on the typical audio-visual elements of translation, but also on the kind of depth that may be needed depending on the product. Thayer and Kolko (2004) pose a three-level model of depth:

- **Basic Localization:** simply textual, leaves GUI (graphical user interface), icons and buttons as they were originally. It is typical in older, text-based video games.
- **Complex Localization:** Way more common these days, it also translates GUI and icons if needed.
- **Blending:** Represents a degree of rewriting of the story to make it better suit the Target Culture. This is way rarer, but used to happen more in the 1990s.

Aside the video game itself, Chandler and Deming (2011) define more levels of translations that may be related to the more commercial part of the product, such as packaging and manuals (also called “box and docs” translation) and dubbing, which is part of the “Full Localization” process, more typical in later, Triple-A experiences.

Game Localization may be subject to heavy censoring, due to socio-cultural reasons or due to the different rating systems, which take different names (for example, Japan has the CERO rating, while Europe has PEGI and the American lands have ESRB – Felini 2015). Aside the elements of attention for clients that can and will be scrutinized in the censoring processes, these are also useful for translators in order to understand what to leave as-is and what to change, depending on the definitive rating that the video game will eventually get.

As for “production times”, video games have many different outcomes in regards of localization. Here are the main two:

- **In-house:** translators and developers work simultaneously within the same company.
- **Outsourced:** outside localizers are chosen from the outside of the developmental process. These people are encouraged to sign an NDA contract and work as “middle men” for the remainder of the production times.

With that being said, despite the work being made by insiders or outsiders, localized games may be released differently depending on developers and production times. Here are the two main ways to release a video game:

- **Sim-Ship:** also known as “Simultaneous shipping”, it involves a complete localization of all versions of the game being released at the same time across the globe within the same day in order to not break the “day one” marketing rule of video game production. The *Pokémon* video games that came out after 2014 all share this kind of localization process.
- **Post-Gold:** this kind of process used to be pretty common around the first years of the 2000s. Localizations in other languages used to take place at later dates, making the video games come out way later in other regions. Some examples of post-gold localized video games may be found in *Earthbound*, *Star Fox*, *Super Smash Bros.*, *Crash Bandicoot* and *Halo*.

Game Localization is usually related to the whole process of translation in video games, although sometimes words and manner of speeches cannot be localized as easily. In that case, Transcreation comes in handy. Diaz Millón (2021) describes transcreation as “a translation-related activity that combines processes of linguistic translation, cultural adaptation and interpretation of certain parts of a text”. Iaiá (2016) defines it as something that is characterized by the greater freedom that translators are given when adapting source texts.

Transcreation is one of the main elements that will be tackled in this thesis later on, specifically relating it to how it is posed in the Italian language.

Italian transcreation is somewhat special, meaning it works around the strategies of the domestication process of translation in order to transpose the “broken” languages of some of the characters represented in video games and re-textualizes its intentionality through the use of retextualizations or diatopic/diastratic varieties, such as Italian dialects or completely different jokes that may work better in the Italian culture.

1-7 - The state of Game Localization in 2025

It is pretty safe to assume that Game Localization as a whole is part of a well-oiled machine and became an integral part of the whole development process after a certain point in time. Despite this being the case, Game Localization has increasingly become more and more of an automated process, with many studies, such as the one conducted by Pirrone and D’Ulizia (2024), stating a certain popularity in the usage of CAT Tools and Unicode, with a lesser presence of AI and Machine Translation that, despite first impressions, are bound to rise in popularity in the near future.

This might depend on many different reasons, first of all relating to localization costs. AI will be cheaper on the long run, but there is still a need for human intervention to handle words and sentences. The role of the localizer, at this point, might be in danger of becoming more of an auxiliary presence, rather than a necessity. Other studies show that AI is already a success in regards of localization of multimedia products. The only part of it that lacks finesse is related to artificial voice generation, but this is bound to change quickly. Of course, as already stated, human participation is still

fundamental, especially in the post-editing and QA process, but AI is bound to be a new frontier in video game localization.

Zone 2: Localizing narrativity and its nuances in video games

2-1 - A deeper look at “*Biomutant*”: Narrativity and Linguistic Rules

As already established, *Biomutant* sets its narrative ground rules in a type of narrativity that is typical of Asian and Norse fairy tales. Aside this clear set of references, the game holds a fair amount of newly established grammar rules that are typical of newborn languages.

First off, the actual written and spoken language in the game prior to the intervention of the narrator has to be as close to the TL of the actual game localization as possible, otherwise the whole experience would not be comprehensible. With that being said, the Italian localization of the game still takes a lot of liberties in order to make it distinct from its English counterpart.

Here are some examples of how *Biomutant* tackles its rudimental linguistic rules:

Case 1: Mongul Mongul

Figure 1. *Mongul Mongul*, English on the left, Italian on the right.

The first case (Figure 1) also happens to be the most important. It has the potential to show how language has evolved in this universe and how it will shape up to be later on, in due time. This first object, a hat, has been named “Mongul Mongul”. While it may appear innocuous at a first glance, this hat represents a true grammatical phenomenon called reduplication. As already stated in the first zone of this thesis, reduplication consists in repeating a word twice to strengthen its meaning. It usually happens in verbal contexts, but it can also happen in nominal phrases, like this one. “Mongul Mongul” does not change depending on the language: both English and Italian name it the same way.

An empirical theory that might come to mind when thinking about how the reduplication process came to be in this context might be as follows: let us assume that these newborn anthropomorphic creatures started exploring more and more, getting inside old human structures and finding old magazines, encyclopedias and the like. At some point, some of them might have started figuring out how to put words one after the other, to the point that they might have seen the slight differences between items and clothing pieces. Getting back to the topic at hand, *Mongul Mongul* might have become a no-brainer for these fantastical creatures. Some of them might have seen old books that depicted this particular hat with the definition “Mongul” as in “from

Mongolia” and then started giving them more and more definitions, like “Regal Mongul” (“Mongul Regale”), for example. Duplicating its definition might have multiple meanings, but this goes even deeper into the realms of speculation.

Speculations aside, “Mongul Mongul” is the main reason this thesis came to be in the first place. It shows how well-developed the language process is in this video game in particular.

Case 2: Mom and Dad

Figure 2. Mooma and Mu-Ma. English on the left, Italian on the right.

Figure 3. Popsi and Papo. English on the left, Italian on the right.

As the four pictures above suggest, the parents of the player are defined with nicknames. They do not possess actual names, nor they matter in the grand scheme of things. Their purpose is purely affective, so every character in the game will refer to them as “Mooma” and “Popsi” for the English version of the game, while the Italian localization will opt for “Mu-Ma” and “Papo”,

which are fairly similar, generally speaking. “Mu-Ma” (Figure 2) is peculiar: its distinction from the English localization is purely morphological, while the sound utterance is quite the same. “Popsi” (Figure 3) might have worked in the Italian localization of the game, but maybe its similarity to the product of “Pepsi” might have incentivized the Italian localizers to choose an easier way, straighter to the point. “Papo” is informal in register. It keeps the same energy of “Popsi”. Both these examples might be good definitions of domestication.

Case 3: Item definitions

Figure 4. "Handle Clampcutter". English on the left, Italian on the right.

All the items in the game can either have invented names or real, “Old World”, definitions. How they might have come to be in this reality is not certain, but the same degree of speculations reasoned before might lead to the idea that some items were better defined than others. Maybe one of these mutant creatures might have gotten their hands onto an old encyclopedia and had the chance to see that the image of a “handle” is actually a handle. With this in mind, words like “Plunger”, “Handle” (Figure 4), or “Tool” actually correspond to “Sturalavandino”, “Manico” and “Attrezzo” in Italian, giving some of the words chosen for the items an actual, non-fictitious meaning.

Case 4: Namings

Figure 5. Jagni, one of the first tribes of the game. Its name is the same regardless of game versions.

Some characters or tribes in the game hold actual names that do not change between language, like it often happens in video games like *Pokémon*, *Kingdom Hearts* or others. Holding the same names gives it a distinct definition that avoids confusion when speaking about specific parts of a game with people that speak other languages, so this type of loyalty holds a huge advantage both for developers and players.

For example, the name “Jagni” (Figure 5), which is related to one of the first tribes that the player meets in the game, are still named the same in Italian, also keeping their distinct “g-n” separated sound and avoiding the common phonological rules of the nasal palatal sound that the “gn” sound holds in Italian.

Case 5: Weapon names

Figure 6. "Extermino Frugrapster". The Italian version changes it to "Genocidio Frugrapster"

Biomutant has a discretely developed crafting system. The player can create their own weapons through the use of many different parts that give it distinct features and statistical advantages. The more pieces are used to create a weapon, the wilder its name. Because of this, it is quite common to see many different composite words or weird mixes between a word and another one. For example, the weapon in the image above is named "Extermino Frugrapster" (Figure 6) in English, while the Italian defines the same weapon as "Genocidio Frugrapster". While not being the exact same, it still holds the definition of something that sounds speedy and is deadly to use.

2-2 – Differences between Italian and English localizations in “*Biomutant*”: specific cases

Other parts of the game got localized in similar ways, still keeping the major elements of the original English localization, while at the same time adapting to the Italian language through sounds and onomatopoeias, which seem to be the main focus of this game, maybe because the language that the creatures speak is not fully developed yet.

Here are some more examples of how the game got localized in Italian:

English Localization	Italian Localization
Surf	Spuma
“Best-Before” / “Out-of-Date”	“Bei-Tempi” / “Ob-So-Leto”
Dead Oil	Mortolio
The Chugyard	Scalo-Ciuf
Jumbo Puff	Pachisbuffo

Table 1.

All of these examples (Table 1) show the differences in approaches depending on languages. The English localization focuses on simple, straight-to-the-point meanings, while the Italian localization goes for a more inventive route, which often coincides with linguistic approaches that are more typical of fairy tales and the like. Something more akin to a writing style that can capture the attention of children, mostly, while keeping a whimsical effect that is distinctive of this game in particular.

Starting off with “Surf”, its Italian translation in “Spuma” is not literal at all. It conveys different things, with “Surf” being more evocative of waves and “Spuma” of pollution and sea foam, which can have an ambiguous meaning. It evokes a more serene, yet menacing, environment, although the wording

choice might be more related to the sound the word makes, rather than its actual meaning.

The second case is related to a single character that has two names. The first one, seen in flashbacks, is “Best-Before”, which is translated to “Bei-Tempi” in Italian. While the joke behind the naming conventions of the character is of course related to how he has aged and went past his “expiration date”, the Italian version of the name drops this meaning, mainly due to it being impossible to lawfully translate, in favor of a name that is more evocative of the character’s looks. This character is dressed like old 80s stereotypical characters, such as the famous rock n’ roll singer Elvis Presley or the “Happy Days” sit-com co-star Arthur Fonzarelli (also known as “The Fonz”), so giving him the definition of “Good-Times”, instead of “Best-Before”, has a less imposing, more nostalgic ring to it. Similarly speaking, this character is named “Out-of-Date” in the present days, which has been smartly translated to “Ob-so-letto”. Of course, the meanings are completely different, with the English version focusing more on the fact that its best times are far gone, while “Ob-so-letto” (“Obsolete” in English) give it a better suited meaning that comes closer to its older name. The good days are over, but he might still have a niche use, after all.

“Dead Oil” is referred to petroleum. Its Italian counterpart goes for a composite word that sounds less menacing and more literal, “Mortolio”. “The Chugyard” is one of the first locations of the main quest. It does have an intimidating definition, being the composition of “chug + graveyard”, with “chug” being related to the sound trains make while moving. The Italian translation follows the hint of a composite word with “Scalo-Ciuf”, ditching the “graveyard” definition and giving it the meaning of a place of passage, rather than one of eternal rest. “Ciuf” has the same role that “chug” has, being an onomatopoeia.

Finally, the first boss the player fights is named “Jumbo Puff”, “Pachisbuffo” in Italian. “Jumbo” becomes the “Pachi” prefix in Italian, maybe being related to “Pachiderma”, which is the definition of an elephant in the Italian language. “Puff” becomes “sbuffo”, which has an analogical meaning, being mostly sound-based. Once more, this localization goes for similar sounding options, rather than actual word-for-word transpositions.

2-3 – Other ways of translating narrativity: “*Stories: The Path of Destinies*” vs. “*Biomutant*”

With *Biomutant* being a mainly narrative-driven game, many questions may arise while analyzing its story-telling processes. Its narrative is mainly non-linear due to the open-endedness of the game, so it does have to be vague at all times in order to make sense depending on how the player decides to tackle the various quests and challenges. Other games might be able to do the same, but this is rarer, if not unusual. One of the games that has a similar, yet completely different approach, is “*Stories: The Path of Destinies*”, An Action Role-Playing Game that came out in 2016 on PC and Playstation 4, and on Xbox One in 2019. Being made by a Canadian studio, *Spearhead Games*, based in Montreal, its main language is English. While *Biomutant* does have a complete localization in both English and Italian, *Stories: The Path of Destinies* is not fully localized, keeping English voices throughout the whole experience. This game recounts the story of a brave fox warrior called Reynardo. He finds himself tangled in a socio-political mess that can either see him as the loose cannon that destroys everything, the brave hero that saves the day, or something in between that usually gets killed in the process. Having 24 different endings, this game takes a while to complete, and that

time is usually covered by witty jokes and storytelling sections curated by the narrator. He has a similar role to the one of the narrator in *Biomutant*, but the differences are apparent in how the game is conveyed throughout the whole experience.

Both games possess the figure of the narrator, but they use it in completely different ways. Here are some examples of the localizations related to the narrators found in both games. They will be analyzed one by one under each table and will be confronted and discussed after its initial observations.

The narrator of *Biomutant*

English	Italian
We're already at the crossroads. Choosing a path in life... <u>It's that fork in the road where you make a choice</u> or simply stop living.	Eccoci a un crocevia. <u>Scegliere la propria strada è come trovarsi a un bivio: puoi decidere di imboccarlo,</u> oppure semplicemente smettere di vivere.
<u>This time, it was best to run and live to fight another day.</u> Let us hope you're ready for it when it comes.	<u>Fuggire, sopravvivere per combattere un altro giorno: la scelta migliore.</u> Speriamo che quel giorno non ti colga di sorpresa.

Table 2.

This section contains 10 examples that can be found in different moments of gameplay. The narrator is the main voice that moves both the plot and the moment-to-moment gameplay, so it is vital to firstly understand how he describes the world around the player, and then how he has been translated in Italian. The narrator found in *Biomutant* holds many whimsical elements that make the game feel more grandiose, structurally deeper than it actually is. His utterances have a weight to them, which goes hand in hand with the whole doomsday-like vibe the surrounding world shows.

These first examples (Table 2) contain some noteworthy segments that have been underlined in order to discuss them. The first sentence that has been underlined is a good example of how the Italian localization tackles the

various challenges of the game. The main point that can be noted is related to word structure. The Italian localization of the game often goes for a more schematic sounding sentence structure (“Fuggire, sopravvivere per un altro giorno: la scelta migliore.”), while the English version leans towards simpler, more literature-like sentences (“This time, it was best to run and live to fight another day.”) This is often a choice of equivalence, which reaches the same goal with different words and sentence structure, so to speak. These first two examples show that sentence structure shifts a lot in the Italian localization of the game, mostly in favor of clarity.

Another noteworthy element is related to subjects. For example:

English	Italian
The Predator isn't the only threat. The wildlife started to mutate when the End of Days began and the Tree of Life started to die.	Il Predatore non è l'unica minaccia. La Fine dei Tempi ha causato una mutazione nella fauna e l'inizio dell'agonia dell'Albero della vita.

Table 3.

This particular extract (Table 3) shows a shift in its grammar. The second sentence is way easier to understand in English, both because it uses simpler words and because it clearly states the subject – “the wildlife” – as well as telling the “when” right away. The same cannot be said in Italian. The subject goes from “the wildlife” to “La fine dei tempi” (“The End of Times”), while “the wildlife” becomes an object (being also translated in “la fauna”) and the original definition of when the “End of Times” began gets ditched in favor of “when the Tree of Life started suffering” (“l'inizio dell'agonia dell'Albero della Vita), instead of being “The Tree of Life started to die”. These shifts in meaning show an oversimplification of sentence structure, as well as a heavier-sounding choice of wording, which can make the complete sentence a bit more difficult to follow. The change in meaning also brings a tonal shift in regards of the Tree of Life, making it “agonizing” in Italian, while the English version clearly defines it already started dying. It could theoretically

be a Neutralization, but this could also be seen as a weird choice, given that the first example of this section (Table 2) clearly cites “simply stop living”, which has the same meaning in Italian (“smettere di vivere”).

English	Italian
The oil sludge is everywhere... <u>To most it only means death</u> , but some have adapted to the new environment and changed with it... Evolution has its ways.	La morchia oleosa è dappertutto... <u>Per molti, un presagio di morte</u> . Altri, però, sono riusciti ad adattarsi al nuovo ambiente, a cambiare insieme a esso... L'evoluzione è ricca di sorprese.
Look, an emergency box from the once-was, a rare sight.	Guarda! Un kit d'emergenza del Mondocheffu. Una vera rarità!

Table 4.

The other two examples above (Table 4) show that the first sentences that have been chosen contain deliberate, arbitrary choices that slightly change the meaning of the words in order to perhaps make the text flow better. It still mostly means the same, so nothing is actually lost in translation for the most part.

What makes this study peculiar resides in the next two examples.

English	Italian
The Morks produce biomatter in their multiorgan that they shed under distress, blobs that affect the regular coding strands of any living being when <u>absorbed</u> , including you.	I Mork utilizzano i propri multi-organi per produrre boli di biomassa, che perdono se sottoposti a stress. Questi boli <u>modificano i filamenti codificanti delle cellule degli esseri viventi. Sì, anche i tuoi.</u>
Blasting everything to bits!	Sforacchiali tutti!

Table 5.

The first sentence (Table 5), although a bit messier in its wording, is basically the same in Italian. The only addition is related to the “multiorgans”, which is explicitly stated in Italian that are “used” to produce “biomatter”. The English localization of the game skips this part to get to the point. It is also important to state that this piece of text is more instructional in its tone in the Italian version, while the English version goes, once more, for a more fairytale-like description. What does make less sense is the omission of the absorption process of said biomatter in the Italian localization of the game.

“Absorbed” is completely dropped as a verb, resulting in a localization that does not actually state how the biomatter should affect the player. It does imply it by saying “Yes, even yours” (“Sì, anche i tuoi”), but it just states that biomatter changes coding strands without getting into much detail after that.

The second example is more on the nose, but at the same time worth pointing out. “Blasting everything to bits” is a sentence that the narrator says when the player starts shooting a lot of bullets with their gun. This, of course, is a manner of speech that cannot be localized in Italian by keeping it as is. Elegantly enough, the Italian localization goes for a quite amusing “Sforacchiali tutti”, which roughly translates to “poke holes in them”, way more playful and joyous, in some way. Most of its joyous definition is due to how the expression is uttered by the Italian narrator, of course, but this tonal shift actually benefits the gameplay, empowering the players to play better and be more aware of their surroundings.

English	Italian
There are few records of the chain of events that led to the big apocalypse eons ago, but it's clear <u>the world wasn't prepared for how recklessly the Toxanol Corporation would make its mark on the world.</u>	Esistono poche testimonianze della catena di eventi che in quei tempi remoti portò la grande apocalisse, ma una cosa è certa: il mondo non aveva idea di quanto profondamente sarebbe stato colpito <u>dalle pratiche sconsiderate</u> della Toxanol Corporation.
Their rare-earth mining and nuclear industries generated tons of waste and, <u>without consideration for the future</u> , they dumped it all in landfills until they ran out of space. That's when they made the <u>BIG mistake.</u>	L'estrazione di terre rare e gli impianti nucleari produssero tonnellate di scorie che la Toxanol, dimostrando una <u>notevole miopia</u> , interrò in immense discariche fino a esaurire lo spazio a disposizione. Fu allora che fecero l'errore più grosso.
They began dumping the toxic waste in the surf just off the coast instead, assuming that it would sink and decay with time. And they were right. But no-one was prepared for <u>what was about to unfold.</u>	Cominciarono <u>infatti</u> a scaricare le scorie tossiche nella spuma a poca distanza dalla costa, convinti che si sarebbero disgregate nel tempo. Avevano ragione, ma non erano pronti ad <u>affrontare ciò che avevano scatenato.</u>

Table 6.

These last 3 examples (Table 6) show once more how the sentence structures have been completely changed in favor of a more textbook-like appearance.

The narrator recounts events of the past that happened way before the mutants came to be. Even if it can be a bit harder to follow than its English counterpart due to its wording choice, it still is quite interesting and compelling to follow through. The first difference worth noting is related to the sentence “the world wasn’t prepared for how recklessly the Toxanol Corporation would make its mark on the world”. This sentence is not completely fluent in English due to its repetition of the word “world”. It has been changed and simplified in Italian with a sentence that literally translates to “the world had no idea of how deeply it would have been hit by the reckless actions of Toxanol Corporation”. The second example sees “no consideration for the future” shifted towards “notevole miopia” (“notable nearsightedness”), while the “BIG mistake” has been completely erased due to its stress not being easy to transpose in Italian. The Italian localization of the last example starts with an “infatti” (“in fact”) that does not exist in the English version, and “what was about to unfold” becomes a provoked action, rather than something unexpected, with “non erano pronti ad affrontare ciò che avevano scatenato” (“they were not ready to face what they unfolded”).

The narrator in *Biomutant* is a vastly different creature in both languages analyzed in this small part of the thesis. It is clear that its different interpretations do not penalize one in favor of the other, but it is important to point out that their different interpretation also deeply changes the tone of the game, bringing the decision on which version has the “better” doomsday vibe up to personal preference, despite all the hiccups that are present in the Italian version.

The narrator of *Stories: The path of destinies*

English narrator	Italian narrator
The two ravens were staring at the kid like he was their dinner. Which probably was what was in their tiny brains.	I due Corvi guardavano il ragazzo come se fosse la loro cena. Idea che probabilmente girava nei loro minuscoli cervelli.
“Hey”, Reynardo said. They cocked their heads at him. <u>“Pick on someone as ugly as you! Wait... That didn’t come out right.”</u>	“Hey,” disse Reynardo. I Corvi girarono la testa nella sua direzione. <u>“lasciatelo stare.”</u>
It was time to talk some sense into the kid. Just hook his way across the ledge and chase the kid down.	Era il momento di ragionare un po’ con il ragazzo. Avrebbe usato il gancio nella sporgenza e l’avrebbe seguito.

Table 7.

Storytelling a more action-focused game can be tricky. There are more variables, more actions that can happen at once, so the narrator has to cover a bit more ground than a slower-paced (to some extent) Action Role Playing Game. The choices made in this game are quite amusing in the long run, but they often do not feel quite well translated. A lot of elements that make the writing style “fun” are missing in the Italian version, maybe because of how many words are written in the same sentence. For instance (Table 7), the first example shown above completely omits the last sentence. “Pick on someone as ugly as you!” is not “lasciatelo stare” (“leave him be”), although its neutralized intention gets to that meaning at some point. Neutralizing this joke makes the Italian translation more bland, less refined and distinctive, because it also misses the “wait... That didn’t come out right” that is still stated in English by the voice of the narrator, but has no written representation. On the other hand, the second example is quite well translated. It misses the sense of urgency that the voice of the narrator eloquently conveys, but still gives all the instructions needed to help the player progress.

English	Italian
Reynardo's blood went up. <u>He just needed to SMASH something!</u>	Reynardo aveva l'adrenalina alle stelle. Doveva distruggere qualcosa.
"Oooh, <u>sparkly!</u> " thought Reynardo.	Oooh! <u>Fantastico!</u> Pensò Reynardo.
Hmmmm. Hero wall. Hero sword. Fire wall... Fire... Extinguisher?	Hmmmm. Muro dell'eroe, spada dell'eroe. Muro di fuoco.... Estintore?
" <u>You blinked!</u> "	" <u>Hai chiuso gli occhi!</u> "

Table 8.

Table 8 above shows four examples of weird linguistic choices when localizing the game in Italian. For instance, the stress and emphasis of the first example "He just needed to SMASH something!" is missing, becoming more like a statement, rather than an actual need of the character. There is no weight to the localization, so to speak, despite it having kind of the same meaning.

The next example localizes "sparkly" as "fantastico" ("fantastic"), which is undoubtedly wrong. It could have easily been translated to "scintillante", instead of "fantastico". The third example of this table roughly translates the same words without catching the fact that the word "fire" should have been repeated once more, so maybe the word "estintore", which actually translates to "fire extinguisher", might have been adapted into something else that could have conveyed a similar intent in word choice. Lastly, "you blinked!" is not "Hai chiuso gli occhi!" ("You closed your eyes"). It could have been transcreated into something similar, like "In un battito di ciglia!" ("In the blink of an eye") to still keep the same eye-related pun, although this can be up for debate.

English	Italian
Reynardo once invested in a jewel store, but it lost money 'cause someone kept robbing him. Twist: it was him!	Una volta Reynardo aveva investito in una gioielleria. Ma si era rivelata una perdita di soldi, perché qualcuno continuava a derubarlo. Colpo di scena: era lui!
Reynardo slinked through Zenobia's ship making no sound at all. Where were her guards? Finally he reached her bedroom. She was curled up on her bed. Ah, he had forgot how beautiful she was, how sleek, how soft.	Reynardo sgattaiolò sulla nave di Zenobia senza fare alcun rumore. Dov'erano le guardie? Alla fine raggiunse la sua stanza. Lei era rannicchiata sul letto. Reynardo aveva

He tapped her on the shoulder with his sword. She vanished and <u>he suddenly noticed he couldn't move aside his mouth.</u>	dimenticato quanto fosse bella, elegante e morbida. Le toccò la spalla con la spada. Lei svanì, e lui si rese conto di poter muovere solo la bocca.
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Table 10.

The two examples above (Table 10) show how more wordy parts of the game can be well localized, even with specific manners of speech or unique words. The only thing worth noting here is related to the end of the second example. “He suddenly noticed he couldn’t move aside his mouth” has a roughly equal translation that simplifies the sentence with less words, deleting the part that states that the character could not move anything but his mouth and putting emphasis on the fact that he could only move his mouth, generating a bit of ambiguity and confusion in the process. Of course, both these examples are not 1-to-1 replicas of their English counterparts, but they still serve the purpose to show that some parts of this game had more care and attention put to it than others.

English	Italian
That is a <u>very cool sword</u> , thought Reynardo. No, seriously. He couldn't feel his paw anymore!	È una <u>spada fantastica</u> , pensò Reynardo. No, davvero, non si sentiva più la zampa.
<u>Boy, if looks could kill...</u>	<u>Caspita, se le occhiate potessero uccidere...</u>

Table 11.

These last two examples (Table 11) are clearly missed opportunities for a transcreation. The first one states “That is a very cool sword”, which can roughly mean that it is indeed “fantastic”, but it misses the point. The joke is related to an ice sword, so stating that it is fantastic (“È una spada fantastica”) makes no sense in the grand scheme of things. Context matters as well, because the joke is furtherly explained in the next sentence, which has been correctly translated. The last line, “Boy, if looks could kill”, can quite literally mean “Caspita, se le occhiate potessero uccidere”, but it entirely misses the mark. “looks” is related to how a character is dressed, not to how they look at others. Maybe this could have been another good case for a transcreation,

turning this clumsy domestication into something that could have made more of an impact.

The two narrators

Biomutant and *Stories: the Path of Destinies* do share the narrator as a narrative element, but their ways to tell the tales of the player are vastly different. Putting the accuracy of the localizations aside, both these games tackled the structure of the sentences in similar ways, putting more emphasis on simple, straight to the point sentences and trying, if and when possible, to simulate the same jokes by translating them literally or finding an equivalent in the Italian language. All of the other cases have been neutralized or oversimplified in favor of an easier translation.

2-4 – Beyond Narrativity: Word-play and composite words in the “Splatoon” series vs. “Biomutant”

Moving on from how narrativity is conveyed in the game, another big part of *Biomutant* is related to wordplay and composite words. As already stated before, *Biomutant* is full of composite words that can be mixed and matched by players themselves when creating new weapons, so the possibilities are endless, even before counting the actual manner of speeches and wordplays already present in the game. The intent for this section is to find a game that has weapons and wordplays that can easily be spotted and discussed, so the “Splatoon” series came to mind right away. All of the examples below come straight from the first two games in the series. The first *Splatoon* game came out in 2015 on *Wii U*, while the second one came out in 2017 on *Nintendo Switch*. They are both *Nintendo* exclusives with a peculiar Italian localization.

This series feels like the best candidate for this type of section, given that this is another post-apocalyptic game with mutant sea creatures that made words up and created their own language, despite it being more of a parody, rather than a complete evolution, of the older, already-existing languages of the world.

English Splatooon	Italian Splatooon	English Biomutant	Italian Biomutant
Baller	Cromosfera	Steepodeepo	Scoscesona
Booyah Bomb	Granbotto	Leftovers	Quelcheresta
Echolocator	Calamaradar	Rubbergrip Pipesharper	Gommopresa Tagliotubo
Inkopolis	Coloropoli	Peekspot	Sbirciatoio
Stay fresh!	In gambero!	Brokenboat	Barcarotta

Table 12.

There is an explicit preference for this part (Table 12) of the thesis to keep as much of the whole table as-is in order to show how similar the linguistic choices seem to be whenever there is the chance to localize wordplay or composite words. Starting off with the first four lines of the table, it is clear how both games prefer a clean-cut, single word localization (aside “Rubbergrip Pipesharper”, which is a two-worded weapon) that evokes similar meanings without actually being the same word. For example, “Baller” evokes the image of a ball in the mind of the player, so the logical translation would be something that defines the item and gives it a shape, so it becomes “Cromosfera” (roughly “Chromosphere”); “Booyah Bomb” gets its Italian definition on the fact that this bomb might be “cool” when exploding, so it becomes “Granbotto” (“Bigboom”). “Echolocator” already sounds like an underwater-specific item, so it has been eloquently localized into “Calamaradar” (Calamaro + Radar) to keep the same meaning while adding a new pun to the mix. “Inkopolis” becomes “Coloropoli”, which holds a similar meaning, but makes it distinctively more *Nintendo*-sounding than other choices, maybe closer to how a *Pokémon* game might be translated (i.e.,

the first generation of *Pokémon* games was related to colors in all sorts of contexts, like “Cerulean City” – “Celestopoli”).

On the other hand, *Biomutant* goes through similar motions. “Steepodeepo”, a mixed-up word that gives the feel of something steep and deep, becomes “Scoscesona” (“Big Steep”) and still holds the same playful meaning thanks to its grammatical augmentation through the suffix “-ona”, which intends to refer to something big in Italian. “Leftovers” changes its meaning through a clever neutralization in the Italian version. Although it literally means “avanzi”, the Italian localization team goes through the route of specification, creating a composite word out of a sentence, therefore “Quelcheresta” (“whatisleft”) becomes the actual name of the location. Back to the topic of weapons, the example of “Rubbergrip Pipesharper” shows one of the many grammatical possibilities that the game offers. The Italian version goes quite lawfully with “Gommopresa Tagliotubo”, ditching the “-er” sound and meaning of the English version, which could have intended that the second word referred to an item that was used to sharp pipes, in favor of something that sounds like an already cut pipe. “Peekspot” (“Postodisbircio”) becomes “Sbirciatoio”, which is basically the same idea with a little more flavor put into it. “Brokenboat” stays the same with “Barcarotta”.

English <i>Splatoon</i>	Italian <i>Splatoon</i>	English <i>Biomutant</i>	Italian <i>Biomutant</i>
“Don’t get cooked... Stay off the hook!”	“Non ci riesci con le mani? Allora tenta coi tentacoli!”	Trim Furfur	Trim Pelbello
Pearl and Marina	Alga e Nori	Notice boards from the long-ago	Raccogli messaggi del Mondochefu

Table 13.

These next examples (Table 13) above show more and more diversions from its original versions, often reaching the realms of transcreation. For example, the first sentence in the English version of *Splatoon* has been completely changed in Italian. “Don’t get cooked... Stay off the hook!” should be “Non

farti cucinare... Stai lontano dall'amo!" in Italian. The difference between the literal translation and its actual translation is related to meaning. The English version has no actual meaning in Italian, because the manner of speech of "staying off the hook", as in "staying out of trouble" does not exist in this form in Italian. The Italian localizers opted for a more elegant solution, based on the poses of the two idols that state this motto.

Figure 7. Alga and Nori, the two idols of Splatoon 2. Their names are different in the English version.

Both of them are related to squids or octopuses (Figure 7), and whenever they close their communications there is a distinct motion made with their hands that resemble tentacles. Despite it being completely wrong from a translator's perspective, the sentence "Non ci riesci con le mani? Allora tenta coi tentacoli" ("Can't do it with your hands? Try with your tentacles then!") still works wonders for the Italian players because the game matches their assonance through the character's poses. Staying on the same topic of this sentence, the characters that state it are named Pearl and Marina in English. They are, of course, names related to the depths of the sea. Curiously enough, these names got localized as well into a new pun, with Pearl becoming "Alga"

and Marina becoming “Nori”, maybe trying to keep the color-coded names through at least one of the names, despite it being swapped. “Pearl” evokes a white color, while “Nori” evokes a darker tone, so this might have been an intention to keep the same type of distinction between the characters through their names.

Going back to *Biomutant* (Table 13), the examples above show another name, “Trim Furfur”, that has been translated to “Trim Pelbello”. The actual name is kept, while their surname got adapted to something more akin to a barber-type character. Of course, “to trim” is not a verb in Italian, but “Pelbello” (“Nicefur”) still evokes the meaning of someone that is good looking and can change the fur of the player. The English version is functional enough, with the hard work being made by a good match between name and surname of the character. What feels more interesting is the next example, where “Notice boards from the long-ago” becomes a mix of composite words that makes wonders for the eyes with “Raccogliamessaggi del Mondochefu”. Both “Raccogliamessaggi” (“Messagegatherers”) and “Mondochefu” (“Worldthatwas”) are full-on sentences that have been glued together to give it this distinct feel of child-like wonder through its composition. These mutant creatures managed to figure out language in a way that sounds both believable and natural to the player. Even though the English version sounds more standardized and easier to understand, the Italian version goes above and beyond to make it distinct and busy-looking.

English Splatoon	Italian Splatoon	English Biomutant	Italian Biomutant
Callie and Marie	Stella e Marina	Flush-stools	Spurga-feci
Check it! Here are the current regular battle stages!	Drizzate i tentacoli, aspolpatori: ecco gli scenari delle partite amichevoli!	Fry-sparkers	Scalda-e-friggi
Great Zapfish	Gran Pescescossa	Citiscenario	Urbanorama

Table 14.

The last 3 examples (Table 14) show how the original release of *Splatoon* inadvertently anticipated some naming conventions of characters, which also explains the reasonings behind some linguistic choices discussed before. First off, the names of the idols in the first game are “Callie” and “Marie”. When put together, the two names become something that sounds like “Calamari”. The Italian version names them “Stella” and “Marina” which is, of course, a similar type of composition (“Stella Marina” is “Starfish” in Italian), but it also conditionally forces a change in the naming of the two characters in the second game, shown in the previous table. So “Marie” is “Marina” (Table 14, Figure 8), while the English “Marina” becomes “Nori” (Table 13, Figure 7).

Figure 8. Stella and Marina, the idols of the first *Splatoon* game. Their English names are Callie and Marie.

Aside this, the next example is related to one of the most frequent sentences the idols of this series say: “Check it! Here are the current regular battle stages!”. This particular sentence comes from *Splatoon 2* (the one with “Alga” and “Nori”), so their version of this sentence is related to their deejay work. The Italian localization of this sentence goes through a different route with “Drizzate i tentacoli, aspolpatori: ecco gli scenari delle partite

amichevoli!” (“Straighten your tentacles, listeners: here are the current regular battle stages!”). The intention of the sentence is still the same, but a couple more puns make the text more vibrant and wordier. It is worth to point out the word “aspolpatori”, which is a pun of the word “ascoltatori” (listeners) mixed with the word “polpo” (“octopus”). This particular change in the word makes it feel right at home in the world of *Splatoon*, which is full of sea-related puns. Then, as the image above anticipates, there is “Great Zapfish”. It got translated the same way in Italian, without any surprises, in “Gran Pescescossa”.

The last three examples of *Biomutant* (Table 14) show how it mainly tends to relate to more and more composite words, instead of going for wordplays like *Splatoon* did. For this reason, “Flush-stools” (“Sgabello di scarico”) becomes a simpler, yet disgusting sounding “Spurga-Feci” (“Feces-purge”), “Fry-sparkers” (“Friggi-scintilla”) become “Scalda-e-Friggi” (“Heat-and-Fry”) and “Citiscenario” becomes “Urbanorama”. This last one sounds like it could be swapped out between languages and the differences would be almost unnoticeable.

Changes and differences

Both *Splatoon* Series and *Biomutant* make great use of composite words, manner of speeches, puns and wordplays. *Biomutant* leans more towards distortions of phrases and sentences, which have a good effect on the world-building aspect of the game. *Splatoon* holds quite the same type of linguistic choices, which is why it has been chosen as a counterpart to confront to *Biomutant* in the first place. The preferences in *Biomutant* make it appear like a world that is still in its infant years of development. Some things have not yet been figured out, so the words have not been completely shaped to preference yet. *Splatoon* shows a world that has lived in that state for a while

at that point. New cultures, characters and ways of speaking make it feel more alive, more socially defined and less jungle-like, although this is only the tip of the linguistic iceberg, because there are many more cases in which more drastic choices have been made in order to make the game more understandable.

Zone 3: The Shortcomings of Game Localization

3-1 – Transcreation Examples in “*Biomutant*”

Transcreation is, as stated before, one tool that will be of use at some point in the life of a localizer. It has the potential of surpassing the untranslatability of jokes and specific linguistic variations at the cost of being faithful to the original text. What is important to remember in regards of game localization and, generally speaking, of adaptation, is that their focus resides on TL, rather than SL. Whenever content is translated into another language, some things are bound to change due to cultural differences or things that would not make sense when translated. One of the best examples of Transcreation might be in the movie “*Back to the Future*”, in which the mother of Marty McFly calls him Calvin Klein in the English-speaking version, while he is named Levi Strauss in the Italian version and, just to bring another example, Pierre Cardin in the French version.

Each version of whatever audiovisual product is bound to have situations like these. This is why there is a completely separated and dedicated section from the rest of the thesis. *Biomutant* is not heavy on Transcreation, but there are some examples that are still worth noting. The idea is to use *Biomutant* as a guideline through the next section of the thesis, looking at four main cases that make more use of Transcreation as a whole. *Biomutant* does not make huge changes between its linguistic counterparts, although it is worth noting that some names got drastically changed in order to fit better in the Italian translation of the game. For example, the word “Chugyard” (Table 1), as seen before, is localized as “Scalo-Ciuf” in Italian. The interesting part is related to the onomatopoeia that has been chosen to convey a similar vibe to the English version. Of course, “Chugyard” does not mean “Scalo-Ciuf” at all,

but this Italian version sounds believable enough to still work and make sense in the grand scheme of things. This is one instance in which Transcreation worked well and made a non-translation completely believable through the use of something that can be similar sounding, but is, with all intents and purposes, completely different in meaning.

Another example of Transcreation might be related to the names of the four main bosses of the game, called “World Eaters”. In the English version of the game, as stated previously, these bosses have a “Puff” suffix that distinguishes them from the rest of the enemies, while the Italian version goes for a similar-sounding “Sbuffo”, which is syntactically the opposite of the example we looked at before. This type of back-and-forth between sounds and specification of what those sounds mean is always present throughout the whole game. So, just to finish the thought, “Jumbo Puff” (Table 1) becomes “Pachisbuffo”, “Porky Puff” becomes “Porcosbuffo”, “Hoof Puff” becomes “Unghiosbuffo” and “Murky Puff” becomes “Buiosbuffo”. Their actual meaning always stays clear, while the “sbuffo” suffix substitutes the “puff” sound, even though some creative liberties are always taken here. The last example of Transcreation in *Biomutant* might be related to the two names cited at the beginning of this thesis (Table 1), “Best-Before” and “Out-of-Date”, which become “Bei-Tempi” and “Ob-so-letto”. They absolutely do not mean the same thing, but the concept of this Transcreation stays intact and makes sense for the Italian rendition of this character.

These are the main differences that can be easily spotted in *Biomutant* when speaking about Transcreation. As one can imagine, the biggest heavy-lifting it does is related to name related to sounds *et similia*, but there are many other ways to transcreate a videogame.

3-2 – Surpassing neutralization: when accents and inflections become full-on linguistic variations through Transcreation

Just like Translation and Localization, Transcreation is always the mean for an end. Conveying something with the same intensity and concept of the original version while changing words and meanings is a big challenge, especially if characters that talk try to communicate through linguistic variations of their native language.

As Gabriele Vegetti, localizer of the video game *Rayman 3: Hoodlum Havoc* answered in a personal interview (available in the appendix of this thesis), “Transcreation depends on the game and context. Games that have a big emphasis on humor are more likely to get the Transcreation treatment, while the same cannot be said for war games, for example.”. Furthermore, as tackled on before, diatopic/diastratic variations “Are rarer these days. Accents are ok, but full-on Italian variations (dialetti) are never advised if the characters did not speak that specific variation before being translated”.

Despite these statements, there are still lots of video games that do make large use of linguistic variations to give more color to the characters, make them more believable and memorable in time. Here are 4 examples of Transcreation in different moments of gaming history.

3-2-1 – Case 1: “*Medievil*” (1998), “*Medievil Remake*” (2019) and “*Medievil: Resurrection*” (2005)

Medievil is an action/adventure video game for *Playstation* that came out in 1998, got a reboot in 2005 on *Playstation Portable* and, once again, a remake in 2019 on *Playstation 4*. It recounts the story of Sir Daniel Fortesque, a weird skeleton man that got killed first in a really ancient war and is somehow remembered as a legend among men. He got resurrected in order to save his land from the dark lord Zarok and, in order to do so, he needs help from all fronts, including old friends of his that still linger as spirits.

The original Italian localization of this game is still remembered fondly among fans of the series due to its charm and humor that are still distinctive and timeless. One of the main reasons the Italian version worked this well is due to the fact that localizers took their time to adapt small nuances and accents of a particular character in full-on Italian linguistic variations, running the risk of being incomprehensible due to its peculiarities.

English	Italian
Dirk: <u>Alright Dan man, how ya doing?</u>	Dirk: <u>Sarve Dani, come va?</u>
Dan: Not too good!	Dan: Non troppo bene.
Dirk: Now then, have ya got yourself a magic sword?	Dirk: Allora? Te sei trovato 'na spada magica?
Dan: <u>No I do not!</u>	Dan: <u>No, non ancora.</u>
Dirk: What? <u>Daniel man</u> , you cannot go into battle against an army of undead without a magic sword... <u>Here take mine</u> , you'll never have to sharpen another blade or my name's not Dirk Steadfast. It's not enough to just have a magic shield, you know, no matter what that <u>soft, thickie Sturnguard</u> says.	Dirk: Cosa? <u>Daniel, ragazzo</u> , non puoi scende' 'n campo contro 'n esercito de' morti viventi senza 'na spada magica. <u>Tie', pia la mia</u> . Non dovrai più affilarne 'n'artra, o non mi chiamo più Dirk il Leale. Non basta avere uno scudo magico, checché ne dica quer <u>ciccione</u> de Sturnguard.
Dan: Great!	Dan: Fantastico!

Dirk: Good lad. Why I'd sooner go into battle holding a tea tray than carry that weedy girl's shield of his!

Dirk: Bravo ragazzo. Io preferirei gettarmi nella mischia con 'n vassoio da tè piuttosto che con quello scudo da donnicciola.

Table 15.

For example, Table 15 shows an extract of Dirk Steadfast, a Scouse accent-sounding hero that gives his Magic Sword to Daniel. His English version is full of character and specific linguistic structures that are typical of informal conversations, mainly shown through his distinctive sounding dialect. It is understandable enough, even for a younger audience, but more specific sentences like “Why I'd sooner go into battle holding a tea tray than carry that weedy girl's shield of his” might pose a challenge, even for older players. This particular dialogue did not change in the remake in 2019. Voices and sentences are the same.

The Italian version goes for a completely different route. Scouse accent is foreign in Italy, so there had to be another way to convey the same cultural impact while keeping it as understandable as possible. The choice the localizers made was to transcreate Scouse into the diatopic variation from the province of Rome, named “Romanesco”. It is humorous in nature and can hold the same amount of impact through the same words. So, “Alright Dan man, how ya doing?” becomes “Sarve Dani, come va?”, with a specific intention of keeping phonological nuances even in its morphological counterpart. “Daniel man”, which shows the addition of “man” as a typical expression of Scouse, becomes “Daniel, ragazzo”, while other parts get more characterization as a compensation, like “Here take mine”, which becomes “Tie', pia la mia”. “Soft, thickie Sturnguard” becomes “ciccione de Sturnguard”. This is interesting, because “Soft, thickie” are arbitrarily related to mental behavior, while “ciccione” goes in for straight body shaming, which, contextually speaking, can have a humorous ring to it. There is also a big emphasis on the Italian pronunciation of the name, with a big, phonetical accent on the first “u” of “Sturnguard”. The last sentence of this exchange

sees Dirk Steadfast explaining his preferences a bit more clearly in Italian, with “Io preferirei gettarmi nella mischia con ’n vassoio da tè piuttosto che con quello scudo da donnicciola”. It still keeps the same effect of the original version, especially on the “weedy girl’s shield”, that becomes “scudo da donnicciola” quite seamlessly. The rest of this exchange is quite loyal to its original counterpart, content-wise. The only notable difference in localization is seen in Daniel, that at one point has his “No I do not” localized into “No, non ancora” (“no, not yet”) for some reason. Lastly, “Dirk Steadfast” is localized into “Dirk il Leale”, which is basically the same.

Moving along, the original Transcreation of the game has been changed at some point, despite it being intact in its latest remake. Another reboot of the game got developed for the *Playstation Portable* in 2005 with some major differences, mainly stylistic, with new voice lines and interactions between characters. Of course, Dirk Steadfast is here once again, but things went for a different route.

English	Italian
Dirk: Howdy Dan, how are ya doin’?	Dirk: Ehi Dan! Come ti butta?
Dan: Sorry?	Dan: Prego?
Dirk: I have to say you’re lookin’ a bit <u>gurney</u> . I told you to stay off the <u>tabs</u> . Are you gettin’ enough <u>chips</u> man? You look like you can do with a good <u>curry or two</u> .	Dirk: Mi <u>sembri tutto ossa</u> ... Te l’ho detto di <u>non prendere quella roba!</u> Sei a <u>posto con tutto amico?</u> Mi sembra che ti serva una bella <u>pepata</u> .
Dan: Pardon?	Dan: Scusa?
Dirk: Now hey man, have you got yourself a magic swordly?	Dirk: Voglio dire amico, ce l’hai una bella spadonza magica?
Dan: What?	Dan: Cosa?
Dirk: What’s that you say? Daniel man, you cannot go to battle against an army of the undead without having yous a magic sword! Are you mental or summit?	Dirk: Cosa dici? Daniel amico, non puoi andare contro l’armata di non morti senza una spada magica! Dai i numeri al lotto o cosa?
Dan: <u>Can I get some subtitles, here?</u>	Dan: <u>Potrei avere i sottotitoli, grazie?</u>

Dirk: Here man, take mine man pet, you'll get nowhere without it I'm telling you.	Dirk: Qui amico, prendi la mia, senza questa non vai da nessuna parte, fidati.
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Dan: Thanks. I think...

Dan: Grazie... Credo.

Table 16.

Things changed drastically here. First off, a noticeable piece is the type of wording. It looks and mainly sounds like Dirk does not want to be understood for some type of gag related to his stronger than before Scouse accent, which, just to add context, happened because of a “shaving accident”. Context aside, the text is way busier and fuller of grammatical inconsistencies that can be typically related to this type of accent. Starting from the first sentence (Table 16), “Howdy Dan, how are ya doin’?” is really similar to its original 1998 counterpart (Table 15). The Italian version translates this to “Ehi Dan! Come ti butta?” which does not respect the original inflections at all. Dan answers “Sorry?”, “Prego?” in Italian. The words are different, but the meaning is the same. He is confused by his question, for some reason. Dirk answers “I have to say you’re lookin’ a bit gurney. I told you to stay off the tabs. Are you gettin’ enough chips man? You look like you can do with a good curry or two”.

There is a lot to unpack. Firstly, the word “gurney”. It has a really negative connotation, mainly related to someone perceived as unattractive or ill. Secondly, Dirk says to “stay off the tabs”, which is clearly related to the use of substances of some kind. All of this got translated as “Mi sembri tutto ossa... Te l’ho detto di non prendere quella roba! Sei a posto con tutto amico? Mi sembra che ti serva una bella pepata”. Maybe the intention is to compensate the original accents with some non-sequiturs, but aside the first part of the sentence that specifies “gurney” as “you’re skin and bones”, the rest is too vague and does not convey the same ideas, maybe because there has been some type of censoring in the translation process (the game is PEGI 7+ in Europe, while the USA has an ESRB rating of 13+). “Stay off the tabs”

becomes “non prendere quella roba”, which does not have context and creates confusion to less attentive players. “Are you gettin’ enough chips, man?” becomes “Sei a posto con tutto amico?”, which does not mean the same, but rather something along the lines of “Are you ok?”, with the last part saying “Mi sembra che ti serva una bella pepata”, which can make sense, but does not complete its meaning, because “pepata” means “something that has pepper in it”, while the localizers surely wanted to translate “curry” into “pepata di cozze”, which is a more typical dish to eat in Italy. With “di cozze” missing, “pepata” makes no sense in this sentence.

Dan follows up with “Pardon?” which is translated with “Scusa?”, and then Dirk doubles down, with the rest of the exchange going quite similarly to the original one of 1998/2019. Some noteworthy points could be “magic swordly” that cleverly becomes “spadonza magica” and “Are you mental or summit”, a strong insult, that gets neutralized into “Dai i numeri al lotto o cosa?”. It is clearly visible that this exchange does not hold any type of accent or linguistic inflection whatsoever in its Italian counterpart. The character speaks in perfect standardized language in its Italian localization, while the English version doubles down on the accents to make it sound weirder and nonsensical. There was a legitimate attempt at conveying the same feeling through the words of the Italian version, but the results lack character due to it being completely neutralized in its accents. All the parts of the exchange that added confusion and color to the exposition like “yous”, “summit” or “take mine man pet” are completely absent in the Italian version, making the visual gag that at the end of the exchange, with Dan saying “Can I get some subtitles, here?” make less sense in Italian, because Dirk is just speaking faster than him, without any type of linguistic variation.

Of course, both translations are valid and represent vastly different interpretations of the character, but this goes to show that it is more and more

apparent that translating accents and inflections is not that common in newer-developed games, with some exceptions.

3-2-2 – Case 2: “*Super Paper Mario*” (2007)

English	Italian
<p>O’ Chunks: GRAH-GOOGLY! So yer the <u>lad</u> stickin’ his ’stachy in me boss’s business! <u>Ye shouldn’t ’ave crossed the count!</u> Now I’m gonna ’ave teh <u>get chunky on yeh!</u></p>	<p>Pugnazzo: PUGNAZZI MIEI! Ahò, ma allora sei <u>te</u> che ’nfilì i baffetti negli affari der capo mio? <u>Nun lo dovevi fà. Nun dovevi infastidi er conte!</u> Mo’ <u>te faccio nero!</u></p>
<p>Pixl: You... You’re one of <u>Count Bleck’s</u> thugs, aren’t you?!</p>	<p>Pixl: Tu... sei uno degli sgherri del <u>conte</u>, non è così?</p>
<p>O’ Chunks: <u>O’Chunks is me name! An’ I’m no common thug, lass. I thug for the count o’ counts, Count Bleck hisself!</u> One word from me Blecky-boy, an’ I come teh make yeh feel some <u>hammage!</u> Hammage? Ehhh... Make that “damage”! Whatever, then! <u>Not that it matters a pinch o’ stew in a sandstorm.</u> Yer a goner!</p>	<p>Pugnazzo: <u>So’ Pugnazzo, se er conte ordina, io ve strapazzo!</u> E nun so’ mica uno <u>sgherro qualunque, bambola. Io so’ LO sgherro der Conte Cenere!</u> Me basta ‘na parola sua e ve riduco in <u>braciolo!</u> Braciolo? Volevo di... “briciole”! Uguaile! <u>Che me ’mporta?</u> Mo’ pe’ voi è finita!</p>
<p>Pixl: Do you even know what Count Bleck is trying to do...?</p>	<p>Pixl: Ma lo sai almeno cosa sta cercando di fare il Conte Cenere?</p>
<p>O’ Chunks: <u>DEH!</u> Me boy’s usin’ powers an’ whatnot teh bring back some order teh this ‘ere world! An enemy o’ Bleck be an enemy o’ mine! They all get chunked! Enough is enough already! <u>It’s time teh tunder down from on high an’ deliver a beatin’ o’ the ages. CHUNK ON IT!</u></p>	<p>Pugnazzo: <u>CERTO, NO?</u> Er conte sta a usà li poteri sua pe’ riportà l’ordine a sto mondo! Un nemico de Cenere è un nemico mio! E lo faccio a pezzetti! Mo’ basta! <u>Mo’ ve riempio de botte come nun v’hanno riempito mai. VE ROMPO!</u></p>

Table 17.

The second case chosen as an example of Transcreation is within an Action Role Playing Platform Game called *Super Paper Mario* that came out in 2007 exclusively for the *Nintendo Wii*. Contextually speaking, Mario has to fight many different enemies in order to find and stop Count Bleck from destroying all of the two-dimensional worlds in the game. One of the first main bosses

Mario will face is named O'Chunks. With his name being a direct pun related to his body size and power (and maybe his shapes, being made of chunky rectangles), it becomes easy to think that this character will mostly be related with physical strength and non-standardized English. With this being the case, O'Chunks looks and sounds bombastic enough to steal the scene for the whole time he is talking on screen. The Italian localization of "Super Paper Mario" translates "O'Chunks" as "Pugnazzo". While it does not mean the same, with "O'Chunks" generally meaning meaning "Di Pezzi" in Italian, his name had to be reworked, so to speak, into something more familiar for the Target Audience. Therefore, once chosen that O'Chunks would have had a strong Italian accent, his name became "Pugnazzo", which just means "Fist" in the English language with an Italian alteration on the suffix ("-azzo") that makes it sound jagged and stronger.

O'Chunks has a strong way of communicating to the player. The example taken for this thesis analyzes his exchange with Mario right before his boss fight. It starts off (Table 17) with an untranslatable exclamation with "GRAH-GOOLY!", which has been localized into "PUGNAZZI MIEI!" ("MY FISTS!"). It does not mean the same thing, but the exclamatory intention still stands. The "Romanesco" Italian variation comes back again to give O'Chunks more character. Most of the pieces that are present in the English version are still present in some shape or form in the Italian localization. The first differences come out from "Ye shouldn't 'ave crossed the count!", which is repeated twice, as well as modulated, in the Italian translation as "Nun lo dovevi fà. Nun dovevi infastidì er conte!" ("You shouldn't have done it. You shouldn't have bothered the Count!"). Once again, the meaning is the same. "I'm gonna 'ave teh get chunky on yeh!" becomes "Mo' te faccio nero!" which holds the same energy and transcreates the "chunky" figure of speech with a similar one that works better in the Target Language.

Curiously enough, the companion of Mario, a fairy named Pixl, answers to O'Chunks and states the full name of the count in the English version, calling him "Count Bleck", while the Italian version keeps it generalized and vague as "conte", maybe for the purpose of keeping the sentence clean and simple. Once again, O'Chunks replies to Pixl stating "O'Chunks is me name! An' I'm no common thug, lass. I thug for the count o' counts, Count Bleck hisself!". The Italian version goes for an extra mile, adding a couple more sentences: "So' Pugnazzo, se er conte ordina, io ve strapazzo! E nun so' mica uno sgherro qualunque, bambola. Io so' LO sgherro der Conte Cenere!". The main difference between these two long sentences stays in the middle of the Italian one, with a rhyme between "Pugnazzo" and "strapazzo", which is non-existent in the English version of the game. Another key difference stands between "I thug for the count o' counts" that becomes "Io so' LO sgherro der Conte Cenere", that puts a lot of stress and emphasis on the fact that O'Chunks is the one and only thug the count will ever need. The English version is instead humbler and gives more attention to the Count, rather than O'Chunks himself.

The next part of his banter sees O'Chunks saying "I come teh make yeh feel some hamage", which becomes "Me basta 'na parola sua e ve riduco in bracirole!". The type of sentence is different, with the first one describing personal agency and the second one being more related to the fact that O'Chunks stays low until the count says otherwise. "Hamage" and "Bracirole", however, have the same type of pun-related impact on the player. It is a humorous way to show this character's illiteracy and lunacy through a clever transcreated joke that keeps the same meaning while being worded differently through Transcreation. Then O'Chunks says "Not that it matters a pinch o' stew in a sandstorm" that becomes "Che me 'mporta", a simpler, neutralized sentence that maybe compensates the lengthier first parts of his line.

After Pixl answers with another question, O’Chunks replies once more with an exclamation, “DEH”, that this time is localized into another question with “CERTO, NO?”, completely changing his intentions. The last manner of speech that O’Chunks gives the player in this section is “It’s time teh tunder down from on high an’ deliver a beatin’ o’ the ages. CHUNK ON IT!”. The Italian version simplifies this section with an informal type of threat, being “Mo’ ve riempio de botte come nun v’hanno riempito mai. VE ROMPO!”. There is another neutralization related to the metaphor O’Chunks chooses in English, while “CHUNK ON IT!” gets modulated into “VE ROMPO!”, which can hold the same meaning, depending on what the English version is trying to convey.

Regardless of meaning, O’Chunks represents another good example of Transcreation that largely keeps the same ideas and intentions of the original character while at the same time changing his connotations and manners, making them closer to Italian-speaking people and culturally separated from his original counterpart.

3-2-3 – Case 3: “*Spyro: Year of the Dragon*” (2000) vs. “*Spyro Reignited Trilogy*” (2018)

Table 18 reveals the next character on the line of the Transcreation studies of this thesis. His name is Crazy Ed and he is a Non-Playable Character (NPC) that comes from the video game *Spyro: Year of the Dragon* that came out in 2000 for the *Sony Playstation* and was developed by *Insomniac Games*. This game sees the purple dragon Spyro going around his world collecting dragon eggs in order to save them from the evil Sorceress and Bianca the Rabbit. Each NPC Spyro meets is bound to give him at least one dragon egg as a

reward for his help throughout the whole game, for a grand total of 149 eggs. Of course, this is not the first instance in which a Spyro game got Transcreated with some diatopic variations, with *Spyro 2: Gateway to Glimmer* having a notable example of a character being Transcreated with a thick Tuscan accent. It is also worth noting that *Spyro: Year of the Dragon* also has other Transcreation diatopic examples, like the NPCs from the level Dino Mines having thick English accents in the Italian localization of the game.

Getting back on topic, the original *Playstation* version of the game sees Spyro meeting up with a Texas-sounding miner named Crazy Ed. He has a job for Spyro related to submarines: if Spyro clears his lake from enemy subs twice, Ed will gift him two eggs. This specific case analyzes the two main lines Ed says in these contexts.

English	Italian
<p>Be careful, roun' dese parts, li'l dragon! Dere be more ghosts in dis here shipyard <u>den I kin shake me pick at!</u> Durned shame, too, 'cause I was mighty close tuh findin' me treasure.</p>	<p>Devi fa' attenzione qui 'n giro, a draghè! Ce stanno più fantasmi in 'sto porto de <u>quanti te n'immagini!</u> <u>Mannaggia...</u> Perché stavo quasi pe' trovà er tesoro.</p>
<p>Dese here waters used to be my favorite divin' spot, but I can't get any loot with dese subs patrollin' around. <u>Think you kin pilot dis here sub I bought for scrap?</u></p>	<p>Qui ce venivo sempre a fa' li tuffi ma non riesco a prendere nulla coi sottomarini che stanno in pattuglia. <u>Che te va de pilotà 'sto sottomarino qui?</u></p>
<p><u>Well, I'll be durned!</u> You've got some mean sub-drivin' skills. Why don't you 'ave dis here egg as a re-ward.</p>	<p><u>Beh, che me possino cecà!</u> Sei bravo a notà. Tiè, prendi 'st'ovo come ricompensa.</p>
<p>Well, I hate t' ask yer help again, but dere be even more subs that durn come outta nowheres. If you could blast 'em, I could use dis <u>acid lake</u> as muh swimmin' hole again. Darn tootin' Git on little dragon!</p>	<p>Beh, me scoccia chiederte de novo 'na mano, ma ce stanno artri sottomarini che vengono fuori dal nulla. Se li distruggi, potrei <u>usa' er lago de novo</u> pe' fa li tuffi. Accidenti, forza piccolo drago!</p>
<p>Hoooooooo, at last, <u>the acid lake</u> is safe fer swimmin agin'! I wish I could re-ward ya better, but all I gots lef is dis 'ere other egg. Maybe dere'll be something better in dis one.</p>	<p>Hoooooooo, <u>almeno se po' notà de novo nel lago!</u> Vorrei ringraziatte mejo, ma tutto quel che c'ho è 'st'altro ovo. Magari c'è trovi una sorpresa più bella in questo.</p>

Table 18.

The original English version goes, as already stated, for a Texas-sounding accent. It becomes more and more apparent the more the character speaks. For example, the sentence “Dere be more ghosts in dis here shipyard den I kin shake me pick at!” clearly shows the peculiarities of this character’s way of talking. The Italian localizers then thought to transcreate his Texan accent into something that resembles Romanesco once again, but with some key differences that will get addressed. The Italian version of the previously cited sentence is “Ce stanno più fantasmi in ’sto porto de quanti te n’immagini!”, which clearly neutralizes the original manner of speech in favor of a clearer one, also changing “shipyard” with “port” (“there are more ghosts in this port than you can imagine!”). “Durned shame” becomes “Mannaggia” (“Damn”) with three suspension points as a follow-up. This goes for an equivalence. The differences between versions start coming up when Ed asks Spyro “Think you kin pilot dis here sub I bought for scrap?”. The Italian localization largely follows the same meaning with “Che te va de pilotà ’sto sottomarino qui?”, but omits the “I bought for scrap” part. Between this sentence and the next one there is a small tutorial part that the character expresses if the player needs help in order to understand how to control the submarine. Both instructions are written in perfect standardized language in both versions of the game, but what makes this part interesting is their phonetics. The English Ed stops talking with the Texan accent, opting for a clearer, standardized English, while the Italian Ed lowers his Romanesco accent, but adds some Sicilian to the mix, resulting in a quite amusing-sounding tutorial.

Back on track, “Well, I’ll be durned!” gets cleverly transcreated into “Beh, che me possino cecà!”. The rest of the text is largely the same until “I could use dis acid lake as muh swimmin’ hole again”, that becomes “potrei usa’ er lago de novo pe’ fa li tuffi”. The meaning is the same once again, but “acid lake” is completely omitted both here and in the next part that cites it, maybe for censoring purposes. The last sentence that cites it says “the acid lake is

safe fer swimmin' agin'!", while the Italian version states "almeno se po' notà de novo nel lago!".

Crazy Ed is maybe the only character that has been transcreated in the Italian version of the game, maybe because of his strong accent. This is not the end of the story, however, because ten years later the first three Spyro games got remade from the ground up by *Activision* in the *Spyro Reignited Trilogy* for *Playstation 4*, *Xbox One*, *Nintendo Switch* and *PC*. Everything was basically the same, aside some small key differences.

English	Italian
<p>You be careful, roun' dese parts, li'l dragon! Dere be more ghosts in dis here <u>shipyard den I kin shake my pick at!</u> Durned shame, too, 'cause I was mighty close tuh findin' my treasure.</p>	<p>Ehi, sta' in campana, <u>draghetto</u>. In questo cantiere <u>bazzicano più fantasmì che navi da rattoppare</u>. Ed è una vera sfortuna, perché mi mancava tanto così per trovare il mio tesoro.</p>
<p>Dese here waters used to be my favorite divin' spot, <u>but I can't get any loot with these subs patrollin' around. Think you kin pilot this here sub I bought for scrap?</u></p>	<p>Una volta facevo immersioni qui, ma <u>con tutti questi sottomarini non si trova più un tesoro neanche a pagarlo. Ce la fai a pilotare questo ferrovicchio, non è vero?</u></p>
<p>Well, I'll be durned! You've got some mean sub-drivin' skills. Why don't you 'ave dis here Egg as a re-ward.</p>	<p>Beh, che mi venisse! Sei proprio bravo a pilotare i sottomarini. To' prendi quest'uovo come ricompensa.</p>
<p>Well, I hate t' ask yer help again, but dere be even <u>more subs that durn come outta nowheres</u>. If you could blast 'em, I could <u>use dis acid lake as muh swimmin' hole again</u>. Darn tootin' Git on little dragon!</p>	<p>Scusa, amico, se ti disturbo di nuovo, ma <u>sono sbucati un sacco di altri sottomarini</u>. Se li levi di mezzo, posso rimettermi a mollo nel mio <u>bel lago acido</u>. Fantastico! Dacci dentro, amico!</p>
<p>Hoohoo! At last, the acid lake is safe fer swimmin' agin'! I wish I could re-ward ya better, but all I gots lef is dis 'ere other Egg. Maybe dere'll be something better in dis one.</p>	<p>Ahuuuu! Ora posso nuotare di nuovo nel lago acido, <u>che sballo!</u> Voglio ringraziarti, te lo meriti, ma mi è rimasto solo quest'altro uovo. Magari in questo c'è una sorpresa migliore.</p>

Table 19.

The transcript above (Table 19) shows the same exchange between Spyro and Crazy Ed. His English counterpart is basically the same, warts and all, while the Italian version got completely rehauled in favor of a neutralized, less distinct-sounding standardized Italian. This results in a character that blends

in with the others despite his original inflections, as well as sentences that both omit and add elements.

First off, “You be careful, roun’ dese parts, li’l dragon!” is localized into “Ehi, sta’ in campana, draghetto”, which is almost one-to-one in meaning and adds a figure of speech to make it more colorful. “Shipyard” becomes “Cantiere” (“Building site”), while “Dere be more ghosts in dis here shipyard den I kin shake my pick at!” is translated into “bazzicano più fantasmi che navi da rattoppare”, which actually transcreates the comparative nature of the sentence entirely with a new one that sounds better in Italian.

Other differences arise when Ed asks “I can’t get any loot with these subs patrollin’ around”. The Italian version of this sentence is “con tutti questi sottomarini non si trova più un tesoro neanche a pagarlo”, which does not mean the same thing as the English version. The original counterpart of this sentence means that Ed cannot reach the treasure if there are submarines patrolling the area, while the Italian translation says he cannot find treasures because there is the implication that the submarines get them before he can. The next sentence, “Think you kin pilot this here sub I bought for scrap?”, gets localized into “Ce la fai a pilotare questo ferrovicchio, non è vero?”, which shows a degree of adaptation as well as an omission and a complete change in the intentions of the question. The original English question asks if the player can perhaps pilot the submarine without assuming his intentions, while the Italian version sounds like Ed is passively assuming the player is going to do it regardless of his input.

The rest of the exchange is localized in a standardized Italian throughout, until it comes to “dere be even more subs that durn come outta nowheres”, in Italian “sono sbucati un sacco di altri sottomarini”, which is basically the same, but omits the “outta nowheres” part. Curiously enough, the “acid lake” part is translated in this new localization as “lago acido”. Lastly, the sentence

“At last, the acid lake is safe fer swimmin’ agin’!” is faithfully translated into “Ora posso nuotare di nuovo nel lago acido, che sballo!”, which sees the addition of an exclamation that is absent in the English version.

Regardless of neutralizations, this third case of transcreation shows the reality anticipated by Gabriele Vegetti, Italian localizer of the video game *Rayman 3: Hoodlum Havoc* (the fully translated interview with him can be seen in the appendix of this thesis). Accents and linguistic variations are not as common as they were before, and this comes with a lot of pros and cons, both related to ways of conveying the same meaning in jokes and manner of speeches. Neutralizing something can increase the risk of not having the same effect in other languages, so it is important to find a way to keep the same type of character despite it not being the same as their original counterparts.

3-3 – Before “*Rayman 3: Hoodlum Havoc*”. Interview with Gabriele Vegetti

Rayman 3 is held dearly by a lot of Italian players that grew up in the 1990s, mainly because of its humor and writing style. This video game was developed by the French studio *Ubisoft Montpellier* and came out in 2003 on *Playstation 2*, *Xbox*, *Nintendo Gamecube* and *PC*, then got remastered later on, in 2012, on *Playstation 3* and *Xbox 360*. Adding this game to the long list of cases chosen for this thesis has almost been a last-minute choice, because I was quite frankly unsure if it fit the bill entirely. The writing style of this game, as already stated, is quite unique and full of specific jokes, so it was vital for me to capture all its nuances before jumping into the actual search for lines. For this reason, I got in touch with the original Italian localizer for *Rayman 3* and asked him a few questions in order to make more sense out of

how the localization process worked back then and how some challenges got tackled. This section will be entirely dedicated to how my interview with him went. The full interview can be viewed in the appendix section within this thesis, while this paragraph will include some extracts that explore the highlights of it.

Rayman 3: Hoodlum Havoc got worked on by Gabriele Vegetti with the help of a proofreader. He had a lot of prior experience with many different games from both *Ubisoft* and other companies like *LucasArts* and *Electronic Arts*. The game got localized from French, its original version, despite English being the first proposition by the company. He most likely had the chance to watch preparatory cutscenes for the game in order to understand context, as well as a glossary that came from the older games in the franchise. The whole localization process took around 3 or 4 months. An interesting tidbit to note about the characters is the inflection of André, the main antagonist, in Italian. He has a thick French accent in the Italian version of the game, while English and French stay standardized. It is uncertain if his accent was decided by *Ubisoft* or during the localization process by him, but what matters is that this is the most notable example of transcreation from French to Italian in the whole game, with some other minor examples fitting jokes and the like. Vegetti had complete freedom while localizing the game. There was mutual trust with the client, so he had more leeway to choose how to localize certain lines, especially depending on the target audience. Transcreation is always important and related to the product type, for Vegetti. Humorous games will get more Transcreation treatment compared to others. Most lines were translated depending on the original audio track, while the voice acting process was produced with Vegetti present most, if not all, of the time, right outside the recording booth. He also had similar moments while localizing other games such as the *Splinter Cell* series from 2004 to 2010 with Italian voice actors like Luca Ward and others.

As concerns how some things got localized in Italian, some jokes would have not made the cut today. For example, hard-hitting words like “Aborto smembrato” (“limbless abortion”) said by one of the characters (translated into “limbless little runt” in the English version) would not be acceptable today because of differences in cultural sensitivities and of course, they would not be repeated again if there was the chance to translate them once more. Vegetti brings interesting observations to the table about the whole process of localization, especially in regards of word spaces and how long should a sentence be in general. It all depends on lip-sync and sound-sync, after all. It is also fascinating to notice how close he worked with the Italian voice actors of the game.

3-4 – Transcreation process in the English language through Case 4: “*Rayman 3: Hoodlum Havoc*” (2003)

Keeping the interview with Vegetti as a guideline for the rest of this section, it is important to choose the right moment of the game to analyze for the sake of this thesis.

With clarity in mind, this part of the thesis will focus only on the home console versions, mainly in the first few exchanges between the characters of Murphy and Rayman. Contextually speaking, Murphy is a green fairy that saves Rayman from the Hoodlums, the grunts of André. This part below happens right when Murphy is flying while holding Rayman by his hair and avoiding Hoodlums. There will be three different versions of the game taken into account: English, Italian and French, the original one. The purpose is to show what type of Transcreation happened between all of the three versions in order to paint an accurate picture of the choices made by localizers.

English	French	Italian
That's all folks, end of cinematic! <u>Time to get down for some serious fights.</u>	Voilà, voilà, voilà! Fin de la cinématique. Maintenant, c'est a toi de jouer!	Murphy: Ecco, ecco ecco! Fine della cinematica! <u>Ora tocca a te giocare!</u>
Oh no, here comes <u>numbskull</u> again. Oh, this place is crawling with them. Ah! They're shooting at us, <u>how original of them.</u> <u>Grab those red things, ok?</u>	Ha, non! Revoilà l'autre <u>tête d'endive!</u> Oh, c'est pas vrai! Y en a partout! Et ils nous tirent dessus! <u>En voilà des méchants originaux!</u> <u>Alors, on m'attrape les machins rouges, d'accord?</u>	Oh no! Ecco un'altra <u>testa calda!</u> Non è possibile, sono dappertutto! E ci sparano addosso! <u>Originale per dei cattivi.</u>
How long are we gonna go around in circles? I'm gonna be <u>b-barfing!</u>	On va pas tourner en rond pendant des heures! C'est un coup à chopper une <u>crise d'épilepsie.</u>	<u>E allora, si acchiappano i cosi rossi, ok?</u>
Ok, you did a little better. I'll reward you with your first parachute jump. <u>Parachute not included!</u>	Bon ok, t'as pas été trop mauvais. Pour la peine, je vais t'offrir ton premier saut en parachute. <u>Sans parachute...</u>	Non si può girare in tondo all'infinito, mi verrà una <u>crisi epilettica!</u>
		Ok, non sei andato troppo male. Per il disturbo voglio offrirti il tuo primo lancio col paracadute. <u>Senza paracadute.</u>

Table 20.

This first section above (Table 20) shows Murphy screaming and shouting, trying to save himself and Rayman from the Hoodlums. This also happens to be a glorified tutorial that shows the player how to recover health by collecting orbs named “red lums”, as well as how to move left and right in order to avoid enemy fire.

The first noteworthy localization happens right away, with French Murphy saying “Voilà, voilà, voilà! Fin de la cinématique. Maintenant, c'est a toi de jouer!” (“There you go! End of cutscene. Now it's your turn!”). This is largely the same among both localizations with one key difference. English Murphy has a Transcreation right at the last part with “Time to get down for some

serious fights!”, which has a completely different meaning compared to the others, but conveys the feel of readying the player in order to be quick and on their feet. Italian Murphy does not change anything, but rather specifies the last part and clarifies with “Ora tocca a te giocare!” (Now it’s your turn to play!”).

Moving along, French Murphy’s “tête d’endive” (“naïve”) becomes “numbskull” in English and “Testa calda” in Italian. Meanings are mainly different between French and Italian, with “testa calda” conveying someone impulsive, dangerous to have around. There is then a slight modulation on French Murphy’s “En voilà des méchants originaux!” (“Now those are some original villains!”) that become “How original of them” in English, with an omission of the word “villains”, and “Originale per dei cattivi” in Italian. The Italian version of this sentence contains all of the originally intended words of the sentence with no compromises, despite modulating its composition to something better suited for Italian audiences.

French Murphy then goes on to say “Alors, on m’attrape les machins rouges, d’accord?” (“alright then, grab those red things for me, ok?”). Italian Murphy says the same with “E allora, si acciappano i cosi rossi, ok?” while English Murphy says “Grab those red things for me, ok?”. The main difference here is in the Italian version, that omits the “for me” part and generalizes the intention of the sentence towards a more generic “someone has to get them” type of deal.

Another difference between versions can be found later on. French and Italian Murphy state “C’est un coup à chopper une crise d’épilepsie” and “Non si può girare in tondo all’infinito, mi verrà una crisi epilettica!”. Both intend saying that, if they do not stop, they’ll catch an epileptic seizure. English version got neutralized and transcreated in “How long are we gonna go around in circles? I’m gonna be b-barfing!”, completely recontextualizing his

discomfort into a more child friendly definition. The last notable part of this monologue sees French Murphy stating “Pour la peine, je vais t’offrir ton premier saut en parachute. Sans parachute...”. Italian Murphy says the same with “Per il disturbo voglio offrirti il tuo primo lancio col paracadute. Senza paracadute” with the three suspension points being omitted, while English Murphy modulates and transcreates its composition entirely by saying “I’ll reward you with your first parachute jump. Parachute not included!”. This got changed so the joke would flow better in English.

This first snippet of dialogue from the game clearly shows how close the Italian and French versions are, syntactically speaking. They hold the same type of jokes, the same sentences with small modulations in between, with English doing the heavy lifting in regards of Transcreation, maybe due to censoring purposes and better contextualization. French and Italian Murphy almost feel and sound identical in both voices and lines. They sound like a fairy actually trying to get out of a sticky situation while cracking jokes to lighten the mood, while English Murphy goes more towards the route of a comedian that tries to distract the player with more condescending lines and wits that can generally be hit-and-miss, depending on the type of player.

English	French	Italian
<p>Murphy: How’s it hangin’, <u>wiener dog?</u> Come on, I’m kidding. Hey, I like that <u>outfit on you. When does it come off?</u> Don’t be so touchy. Here, check out what I found. The manual! It’s all in here, <u>if you read the story you’ll find your way out.</u></p>	<p>Murphy: Alors, comment ça va, <u>la saucisse?</u> Heé, je déconne. T’es vraiment trop bonne coma ça, tu sais? D’ailleurs, c’est grand que tu <u>enlèves le bas?</u> Bon, le prends pas comme ça. Tiens, regarde que j’ai trouvé! Le manuel! Y a tout là dedans. Si on lit l’histoire, on <u>trouvera comment te tirer de là.</u></p>	<p>Murphy: Allora, come va, <u>salsicciotto?</u> No, sto scherzando. Sei molto sexy così, lo sai? <u>Ma quand’è che ti levi le calze?</u> Dai, non prenderla così, guarda, che cosa ho trovato. Il manuale! Qui c’è tutto! Se leggiamo <u>scopriremo come cavarcela.</u></p>
<p>Once upon a time there were lums, harmony, love, <u>peace, boring!</u> Suddenly, a black lum transforms the</p>	<p>Alors, il était une fois les lums... l’armonie... l’amour... la paix... Tu parles d’un scénario...</p>	<p>Allora, c’era una volta i lum, l’armonia, l’amore, la pace, ah <u>ma è una sceneggiatura!</u></p>

<p>red lums in hoodlums, the world is in great danger! Oh, here we go, here we go, it says here that Globox took off with your hands!</p> <p>Rayman: Knowing what a scaredy cat he is he's probably hiding some place.</p> <p>Murphy: It's not gonna be easy to get your hands on him... hands, no pun intended. What? This is out of control! The manual claims you can make a chopper out of your hair! Make a chopper of your hair... huh. <u>Sounds like someone's been eating paint chips again.</u></p>	<p>Soudain... <u>Le drame...</u> André transforme les lums rouges en hoodlums... le monde est en danger... Ah, voilà. Là, ils disent que c'est Globox qui est parti avec tes mains.</p> <p>Rayman: <u>Trouillard</u> comme il est, il a du se planquer quelque part.</p> <p>Murphy: Ca va pas etre évident de lui mettre la main dessus. Surtout pour toi. Attends, trop mort de rire. Le manuel dit que tu peux faire de l'hélico avec tes cheveux. L'hélico avec tes chevaux? <u>Ils ont fumé ou quoi?</u></p>	<p>All'improvviso André trasforma i lum rossi in hoodlum, il mondo è in pericolo! Ah, ecco, qui dice che Globox se ne è andato con le tue mani.</p> <p>Rayman: Beh, fifone com'è sarà nascosto da qualche parte.</p> <p>Murphy: Non sarà facile mettergli le mani addosso, soprattutto per te! Aspetta, è troppo buffo. Il manuale dice che puoi fare l'elicottero con i tuoi capelli. Un elicottero con i capelli? <u>Ma cos'hanno fumato?</u></p>
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Table 21.

The extract in Table 21 happens right after Rayman is left falling down to safety. Murphy reaches him once again to see if he is ok. French Murphy starts off with “Alors, comment ça va, la saucisse?”. Italian Murphy says the same with “Allora, come va, salsicciotto?”. English Murphy gets transcreated into “How's it hangin', wiener dog?”. “Sausage” would have been the actual meaning of “saucisse/salsicciotto”, but due to its definition being ambiguous, English localizers must have chosen a more kid-friendly version to convey the same meaning. French Murphy then does sexual allusion jokes about Rayman's appearance, concluding his banter with “T'es vraiment trop bonne coma ça, tu sais? D'ailleurs, c'est grand que tu enlèves le bas?”. This roughly means “You're really too good looking, you know? By the way, is it too big to take off your bottom part?”. The context here relates Murphy's jokes to Rayman, a limbless character, not having hands because they got stolen from his best friend, Globox. This is important to note because Murphy's statements have the precise intent to lighten the mood with non-sequiturs that

stun and try to make Rayman and the player laugh at the same time. The Italian version transcreates this joke in particular by specifying the first sentence and then changing the second – “Sei molto sexy così, lo sai? Ma quand’è che ti levi le calze?”. The meaning is roughly the same, of course, but the first specification, along his mocking tone, sell the joke in a better way that then gets closed off with a better, kid-friendlier “when do your socks come off?” instead of being a more generic “bottom part”. A funny coincidence to note here is that Rayman actually loses his shoes a few times during the whole experience of gameplay, with him becoming small and riding his right shoe, trying to catch his left one that went berserk. English Murphy transcreates the joke once more by saying “Hey, I like that outfit on you, when does it come off?”. It generalizes its meaning, keeps the same joke but does not localize what part of it should come off.

Murphy then takes the actual manual of the game out of his pocket and says in French “Le manuel! Y a tout là dedans. Si on lit l’histoire, on trouvera comment te tirer de là”. Italian Murphy kind of says the same but omits “histoire”, saying “Il manuale! Qui c’è tutto! Se leggiamo scopriremo come cavarcela”. English Murphy keeps “histoire” with “The manual! It’s all in here, if you read the story you’ll find your way out”. French Murphy then starts reading the manual and states “Alors, il était une fois les lums... l’harmonie... l’amour... la paix... Tu parles d’un scénario... Soudain... Le drame... André [...]”. This is generally the same sentence in all language, if not for a key difference in the last phrase, where “le drame” (“drama”) gets omitted throughout. Italian Murphy changes the list of things that French Murphy says, omitting the suspension points, with something faster to follow “Allora, c’era una volta i lum, l’armonia, l’amore, la pace, ah ma è una sceneggiatura! All’improvviso André [...]”. The main difference here, aside the evident syntactic modulation, is the transcreation of “Tu parles d’un scénario” into “ah ma è una sceneggiatura!” (“ah, it’s a script!”). It changes

intention, as if Italian Murphy did not notice that he was reading a script before reaching that point. English Murphy gets transcreated even further in “Once upon a time there were lums, harmony, love, peace, boring! Suddenly, a black lum [...]”. Transcreation is found here in the statement discussed before in regards of the manual being a script. English Murphy just states that what he is reading is “boring”. It then follows through with André being generalized into “a black lum”.

Lastly, when Rayman and Murphy start moving, the fairy gives him advice on how to move around. French Murphy states here “Attends, trop mort de rire. Le manuel dit que tu peux faire de l’hélico avec tes cheveux. L’hélico avec tes chevaux? Ils ont fumé ou quoi?”. Italian Murphy follows suit with “Aspetta, è troppo buffo. Il manuale dice che puoi fare l’elicottero con i tuoi capelli. Un elicottero con i capelli? Ma cos’hanno fumato?”. What matters here is the joke at the end, in which Murphy insinuates that who thought about this idea must have smoked a lot before writing it down. This got transcreated and neutralized in English with “What? This is out of control! The manual claims you can make a chopper out of your hair! Make a chopper of your hair... huh. Sounds like someone’s been eating paint chips again”. The joke has become more kid-friendly, excluding the “smoking” part entirely.

As Vegetti stated before, trying to localize the game from English would have resulted in different interpretations of the same jokes, the same type of differences that can be found here between French and English, therefore between Italian and English as well. The English version of *Rayman 3* is almost in its own vacuum, to some extent, due to its different interpretations and neutralizations of some sexual innuendos, for the most part, and to the role that Murphy covers throughout the start of the game. The Italian version of the game is instead a truthfully faithful interpretation of its original French counterpart that keeps almost everything while still keeping a PEGI age 3+ rating in its original release, bumped up to 7+ in the HD versions.

Zone 4: Let us discuss it

4-1 – To sum it up: the impact of narrativity in video games

Very few games share the same characteristics of *Biomutant*, narratively speaking. Of course, as stated many times before, *Biomutant* follows some narrative tropes that have been well-established in writing history, despite the presence of a narrator recontextualizing everything. Narrators are not usually that appreciated in the video games media, when so prevalent. They can either be an integral part of gameplay that enhances thought processes and does not get in the way, like the narrator of the 2011 video game *Bastion*, or a more encumbering presence, like the ones from *Stories: The Path of Destinies* and *Biomutant* itself. What is important is how the stories they recount are conveyed. With the latter two being wordier games, the development of their plots looks and sounds busier and a bit more confusing even for seasoned players. Despite this, both latter games show a type of dedication to the moment-to-moment gameplay that is still relatively new to this day. The examples shown in previous Zones clearly show *Biomutant* being a breathing, living product that has the potential of standing on its own two feet thanks to its way of communicating to the player. Its narrativity gives ample space to a type of philosophical interpretation that only a post-apocalyptic game could give. On the other hand, the playfulness of *Stories: the Path of Destinies* generally stays intact despite something being lost in the localization process.

The narrative that these two games have shown throughout the whole thesis is not only a means to recount a plot, but also a way to entice the player and invest them to focus on it and see it through. *Stories: the Path of Destinies* does this thanks to its many ways of lightening the mood and describing the characters right outside the video game vacuum (i.e. in Table 10 there is a

joke about Reynardo investing in a jewelry once, which is completely unrelated to the game plot, but gives the character more depth), while *Biomutant* opts for a more classic approach that focusses on told experiences that the main character does not remember most of the time. Many of the characters do repeat themselves a lot of the time they talk because of this, but this does not mean the plot gets padded out in order to meet certain criteria. On the contrary, the characters the player meets talk almost non-stop, to the point that the narration of the game gets enhanced through their words and their perception of the player and the world around them. The characters of *Biomutant* do resemble specific archetypes and there is no intention to hide it whatsoever. Their “weirdness”, so to speak, is nothing but a complementary element that gives the game more landmarks and memorable set-pieces. With that being said, narrativity in video games still holds the importance that has been described at the beginning: when a narrator is present, there is a need to tell a story. How this story unfolds depends on many factors, like the genre of the video game, its artistic choices, so on and so forth.

Biomutant chooses a classic approach that can look “tired” when compared to other ways of story-telling, but still has many aces up its sleeve in order to invest the player and have them enjoy the game as-is, surpassing any type of review or judgement about the game. In the same vein, *Stories: The Path of Destinies* has a narrator that focusses more on jokes and simplification. The whole shtick of the game has been built around the fact that the story is bound to repeat itself due to the multitude of possible choices and endings, so this means that the player will be forced to explore the same maps over and over again, with the narrator saying something slightly different every time depending on context. What endings have been unlocked? Which ones have not been seen yet? This question alone gives context to what the narrator will say next. Narrator-driven games have to cover a lot of ground that depend on

what the player has done and what has not been done yet, and this is also true for *Biomutant*.

This type of attention to detail has the potential of building a video game that has many differing outcomes within the same gameplay; therefore, it needs a type of love, care and time put into by the developers that is no easy feat. Some games managed to reach this type of variability and paid this feature with longer development times, like 2023's *Baldur's Gate 3*, for example. These are a dime a dozen, however, so they cannot actually represent a real, one-size-fits-all possibility. Games like these have so many variables that it is impossible to anticipate how its narrative will be if the time, effort (and budget) put into it do not increase. For that reason, it is sometimes wiser to choose, as a developer, smaller experiences that give more leeway for simpler narrative structures that can be easily predicted and developed, and for that both the narrative samples chosen fit the bill entirely.

4-2 – The power of wordplay

Games like *Biomutant* need to have a distinct way of defining their own world, hierarchies and items. While *Biomutant* does this expertly through the use of real-world linguistic rules and mixes them with imaginary definitions and onomatopoeias, it is worth noting that it is far from the only game that tackles this type of structure, sentences and phrases. There is a plethora of games that make use of wordplay, with most of them being related to *Nintendo* and its own Intellectual Properties. Of course, the *Splatoon* series is maybe the easiest to point at because it is fairly recent, but others, like the *Pokémon* series, the *Pikmin* series, as well as *Metroid* games among others do have the same amount of care put into it, linguistically speaking. Finding the right balance between fantasy-like naming and information within the same

word-frame can be quite challenging, but both *Splatoon* and *Biomutant* managed to pull it off in a way that feels distinct enough and interesting to follow.

While *Splatoon* is classically set on a specific track that does not change its course throughout the whole gameplay experience, *Biomutant* opts for something similar, which gets enhanced whenever the players feel empowered to craft their own weapons and create their own ways of defending themselves. Being a “looter” – namely, a game in which you collect as many pieces of scrap as you can – *Biomutant* has a huge quantity of mixes and matches that can almost literally create new words and sentences through the creation of a new weapon. This system has its limits, of course, but the point stands while discussing the degree of care and attention put into how a game communicates and shows its colors. With its definitions being almost *Nintendo*-like, *Biomutant* reveals itself to be a great linguistic experiment that gives power to the players and shows a great degree of imagination.

4-3 – The people who originally worked on the Transcreation case studies

Transcreating a video game is never an easy choice, that much is certain. The sample taken from the games that have been looked at as cases do contain a lot of interesting examples of Transcreation that have made popular history to some extent. Choosing for a diatopic variation when localizing a character has been quite risky in regards of clarity, but the end result has been coherent enough to the source material that it left a mark. For example, despite *Medieval* (1998) got worked on by only one person, Andrea Masneri, his localization still stood strong in the *Medieval* remake from 2019, with Claudia

Gibbardo leading the whole localization process in-house and Emanuele Giordanengo taking the role of tester. The work of Andrea is still relevant today despite being 21 years old, all things considered, strengthening the fact that a good Transcreation and loyalty to the original source help keeping the ideas of the first video game perfectly intact throughout. *Medievil Resurrection* got worked in-house by Domenico Visone, who has been quite active around the same times that this game came to be, with titles like *Killzone HD* and *Ape Academy* being notable examples.

In regards of *Super Paper Mario*, it got localized in-house the same way *Splatoon* did. Three people worked on it, with two of them (Christian Massi and Daniele Braglia) still working with *Nintendo* as of 2025 on video games like *Mario & Luigi: Brotherhood* and *Xenoblade Chronicles X: Definitive Edition*. The third localizer, Monica Citi, worked on less titles around the same time of this game, such as *Fire Emblem: Radiant Dawn* and *WarioWare: Smooth Moves*. The kind of love and attention that is put into every detail and accent of *Super Paper Mario* clearly shows how this localization work got tight-knit schedules and clear focus on conveying the same things that originally got written into another language.

Figure 9. Credits in the *Spyro: Year of the Dragon* Italian Booklet.
Thanks to the user Tinyfusion from the Crash Bandicoot Zone Telegram Group!

With *Spyro: Year of the Dragon* some things did change. First off, there are no clear signs if its localization got done in-house and who actually worked on it, if the only reference to look at is the video game itself. If one takes a look at the Italian booklet of the game (Figure 9), Domenico Visone pops up as the Italian localizer for the game once again, just like in *Medieval Resurrection*. What is certain is the fact that Crazy Ed's Romanesco got neutralized in *Spyro: Reignited Trilogy*, which has certainly been localized in-house by at least 2 people that were already with *Activision* at that point in time, maybe under some type of contract as freelancers, namely Alfio Federico Di Pinto, whose most recently localized game is *Among Us* for *Playstation 5*, and Francesco Iorio, who only worked on one other game, *Call of Duty: Black Ops IV*.

Lastly, *Rayman 3: Hoodlum Havoc* got outsourced to *Orange Studio*, led by Gabriele Vegetti with the help of a proofreader whose name is unknown. They localized the game from French to Italian, as already stated. *Rayman 3 HD* got ported as-is, so his original work did not change whatsoever.

All of these historical distinctions have been made in order to neatly document them first, and secondly to show how different times ask for different working crews that inevitably increase in numbers, with examples like *Medieval (2019)* and *Spyro: Reignited Trilogy* that count at least 11 localizers working together on different versions of the game.

4-4 – What did *Biomutant* leave in the current video game landscape?

The current video game landscape does not really show the impact of how *Biomutant* did its job, although it is worth to note that the game came out at a moment in which Action Role Playing Games were slowly shifting towards clarity, rather than intentions and conveyed feelings, even from a simple teaser trailer. This also meant that big ceremonies like *The Game Awards* have shown how the preference of the public shifted from open-world experiences (that, at this point, have been the norm) to more linear experiences, like *Stray* in 2022 or *Astro Bot* in 2024. As concerns its localization, *Biomutant* still looks like a special case among others. There have been some examples that resemble this type of writing in prior years, but nothing has come close to how *Biomutant* refers to itself and its own environment. The localization studio that worked on *Biomutant*, Keywords Studio, has worked and still works today on game localization, with their first attested localized game being *Gang Beasts* in 2014 and their latest notable release being *Mafia: The Old Country* in 2025. This game in particular is a great example of Transcreation. The original English version has a mix of Italian and English with a thick Italian accent (and some Sicilian sprinkled in), while the Italian localization goes the extra mile with a distinct Sicilian accent due to the game being located in Sicily. Getting back to *Biomutant*, it is important to note that

Keywords Studio has worked on different localizations of the game, namely Italian, French, Hindi and Indonesian. Keywords Studio has worked on a lot of games since *Biomutant*, so it could be fair to assume the studio itself has learned from its past, both from positive and negative experiences. Therefore, despite the fact that *Biomutant* might not have had a huge impact on the localization of video games, its case still stands strong as a great example of localization from English to Italian that should be remembered as a great sample of creative liberties on certain types of sentences or interpretations.

4-5 – Differences in game localizations

It is no secret that localizing a video game has its fair share of headaches. *Biomutant* surely had its challenges to overcome, but it is not the only game that needed attention in this regard. The games that have been chosen for this thesis all have common elements. *Stories: the Path of Destinies* has been chosen because it has a narrator figure that is clearly similar to the one of *Biomutant*, despite a first drafting of the thesis did not even consider it as a possibility. Another game, *Tearaway: Unfolded*, was the original first candidate, but did not fit the bill entirely. These three games in particular have matching narrators. Their role is to guide players, give them feedback, empower them depending on what they do, as well as elevate the plot when the game needs it. Of course, every game does it differently, even the ones chosen for this thesis do not do it the same way, although what matters is how the narrators refer to the player through their words and how they make them feel.

The main difficulties of this first section were completely related to finding the right examples to choose in order to show differences. Most of them have been taken from the beginning parts of their respective games, with some

small other examples coming from non-plot related moments that still held a good degree of discussion. The objective here was to show all types of approach to the localization process. There are some great examples of modulation from both games, as well as perfectly serviceable localizations that are almost 1-to-1, with some others that went for omissions or missed some marks entirely. The point of this comparison between narrators is related to how time, space and experience can make a big difference in the grand scheme of things. The game localizers for *Stories: the Path of Destinies*, Roboto Global, has a similar history to Keywords Studio. They, too, have worked on a lot of games, but started in 2009, 5 years before. With both studios being quite similarly experienced in this regard, these games looked perfect for a narrator comparison.

Moving on, the next comparison that needed to be addressed was related to word play and composite words. *Biomutant* has a lot of examples like these that need to get addressed in some form, so finding a game that could serve a similar purpose in this regard was a challenge in it of itself. *Nintendo* games have had similar works put into them, so the best bet was *Splatoon*. The choice of putting the first two games in this thesis instead of only one of them is because their writing style is quite different. *Splatoon 2* is more flashed out throughout, so it made sense to make a mix-up of games in order to show the many interpretations of the same words or similar definitions, weapons and the like. Both *Splatoon 1* and *2* got localized internally within *Nintendo* Headquarters, so their work was done in-house.

Choosing the right way to localize something can be a hard task, generally speaking, but all of these examples might have hopefully shown that there are no clear-cut solutions to most situations. Modulating, Omitting, Compensating, Adapting etc. are always choices that depend on context, untranslatability, ambiguity and uncertainty of what could be lost within the localization process. Sometimes it is best to adapt and make more sense out

of something that can be similar (i.e. “Chugyard” / “Scalo-Ciuf”) rather than opting for loyalty to the original. At the same time, it is best to choose loyalty to its original counterpart in order to make life easier for both localizers and developers, so that ambiguity will not be an issue later on and things will not need to be changed in order to make sense (like it happened to the idol names in *Splatoon 1* and 2).

4-6 – When is Transcreation used?

Creative liberties on meanings

The biggest challenge to overcome for every game localizer happens exactly when a sentence cannot be easily translated. Sometimes it can happen because of manner of speeches, other times because, culturally speaking, some quotes in the game do not have the same type of impact in other cultures. When this happens, the Domestication process comes to help through Transcreation. It can be seen as a separate type of Translation due to its variety of approaches, but one point still stands at the center of it all: if something cannot be translated, something equivalent has to be found as a substitute.

The examples that have been chosen in Zone 3 are exactly that: snippets of gameplay that show the potential of linguistic variety, warts and all. While professionals of the localization process do have their doubts about the results, especially in regards of player comprehension, it is still important to remember that Transcreation is sometimes quintessential in order to make a game work in different languages. While most examples of Transcreation come from the earlier generations of consoles, there are still some important examples that show its true potential. One of the most notable later examples of Transcreation can be found in the 2017 *Square Enix* game *Dragon Quest XI: Echoes of an Elusive Age*, which contains some dialogue with heavy

diatopic variations that depend on NPC locations and the like. Other games, like the already quoted and most recent *Mafia: The Old Country* that came out on August 8th, 2025, as well as “games as a service” titles like *Hearthstone* or the MMORPG *World of Warcraft* still hold a great degree of Transcreation.

All of the previously mentioned titles can easily show how Transcreation can go either way in the game localization process. It sometimes works great, like in *Medieval*, *Spyro: Year of the Dragon* or *Super Paper Mario*, but it is really easy to slip up and become incomprehensible, so there has to be a balance between the inflections of the character and their informativity.

4-7 – Creative narration in a post *Biomutant* world

While it might be safe to assume that *Biomutant* did not leave a legacy after itself due to its unjustifiably lukewarm reception, there have been a lot of video games that continued exploring the realm of narrator-driven games. Some examples include 2022 games like *Bramble: The mountain king* and *Beacon Pines* and 2023’s exceptional Role-Playing Games like *Baldur’s Gate 3* and *Disco Elysium*. As already stated before, these narrators do not have the same role of the one in *Biomutant*, so the inclusion of a figure like this in a video game will have a different function altogether.

While *Bramble* and *Beacon Pines* use the narrator as a way of steadying the rhythm of the story and make it progress, the ones present in *Disco Elysium* and *Baldur’s Gate 3* usually relate to the player’s choices like a moral compass that really does not look for the best outcome, but rather for what they feel is right for the player in particular at that moment in time. For example, the narrator in *Disco Elysium* takes many different shapes and sizes, like a lens that helps the main character in his quest and gives way to parts of

the psyche of the main character related to what has been chosen and what has been leveled up skill-wise. Players that choose to be more empathetic will also have a more methodic, thoughtful and charismatic narrator, while the ones that choose to level up skills like “Electrochemistry”, “Shivers” or “Physical Instrument” will have a more impulsive narrator that will not take others into consideration and opt for more drastic choices.

Like all the examples above, narrators can be different depending on the type of game that players will tackle. *Biomutant* did not have a big impact on the gaming industry, but this does not mean it has done a bad job altogether. On the contrary, its narrator-driven plot needs to be remembered and studied for future gaming experiences that might need that “something else” to enhance it.

4-8 – What lies beyond

I would like to finish this thesis with a look at the future. “What lies beyond” is somewhat evocative, I reckon, but it also gives a chance for everyone who will read this thesis to reflect on what has been done until now in regards of game localization and what can be done in the future. What has been explored, what should be explored more, what can be taken from this study.

The world of video games explored many different genres and types of experiences that today can be seen as “the norm”. Video games that back then were seen as “innovative” like *Super Mario Galaxy* on *Nintendo Wii*, *Half-Life* on *PC* and *Gears of War* on *Xbox 360* have left a great impact on how the industry presents itself and how a video game genre “should be made”. Of course, there is never a clear answer to how something should always be made, but following the same path that someone else paved before is almost

never a bad choice. The same can be said for Game Localization, to some extent. Trial and error are the lifeblood of the subject, so I would argue that experimenting with wrong turns and what appear to be “mistakes” should be quintessential for the progress of Game Localization and Translation as a whole. Nothing is ever perfect, so it would be cool to try new stuff out in order to see what happens. Having fun with a subject is always the best way to improve and understand its deeper mechanisms, so my best wish is to explore even more and be creative while doing it. Finding new ways to localize difficult sentences, creative solutions to ordinary linguistic issues and the like.

In regards of what should be explored more, I feel like Transcreation should be taken into account as a type of Localization that can and will work depending on context. Of course, diatopic variations should be only used when needed in order to keep clarity, but I see no reason to neutralize accents and linguistic inflections when Transcreating a text, or a character, or a story altogether, if the text can be re-written clearly and can easily be understood from its readers while keeping the inflections.

Lastly, this study has the precise intent of showing what can take place during the process of a Game Localization, with some examples of Transcreation that make use of diatopic variations when needed. All of these examples should hopefully show that there is a great degree of possibilities that can be tackled in so many different ways. So, while the answer to most questions related to the discussion might be that “everything depends on context”, it is also important to remember that it is the context itself that constitutes the reasoning behind one translational choice or another.

Now for the million-dollar question: what lies beyond in the game localization world? While it is not easy to predict what will happen in the future, there are some clear elements that can give somewhat trustworthy

estimations. Professionals in the field like Gabriele Vegetti state that AI, LLM and Machine Learning have almost become the norm, with a big increase in clients asking for its use in order to simplify the process and cut costs. Despite this, Vegetti explains that it is always important, if these tools are used, to verify the completed work in order to always have the “last word”, so to speak. With that being said, it is always important to remember that creativity and user input will always precede these types of instruments.

Conclusions

Biomutant is a great example of how a Localization can be tackled in order to maintain its faithfulness to the original English version while at the same time constructing a believable world that differs from the rest, even in the actual vacuum of the game. *Biomutant* has been localized in four languages by Keywords Studio. Their work has been generally great, with a lot of modulations, very few omissions and a lot of Transcreational work, especially when related to sounds or composite words. Onomatopoeias are also quintessential to localize in this video game, because its characters do speak through them depending on the context. With its strong identity enhanced through manners of speech and sounds, *Biomutant* holds a lot of character and is, generally speaking, a good localization throughout with very few weak points, none of them worth noting.

There have been some games with similar ways of speaking or with narrator-driven plots. Some of them have been listed and discussed in this thesis. While the plot structure in *Biomutant* is revealed to be quite common among fairytale-like video games, its deeper gameplay mechanics are interesting spins on what has already been tested in 30+ years of video game history. Therefore, while some of its characteristics might be fairly common in the video game landscape, *Biomutant* still stands on its own enough to feel original. The games that are mostly similar to *Biomutant*, gameplay-wise, might be some hack 'n' slash titles like *Diablo* or Action Open World Role Playing Games like *Assassin's Creed* or *Immortals: Fenix Rising*. This is never a 100% match, thankfully because two things can never be the same, but they can get close. While *Biomutant* is a hybrid approach between a looter game and an Open World, other video games tend to focus on one element and stick to it throughout the whole experience, such as the titles mentioned before. In this regard it is then safe to say that *Biomutant* can be quite unique despite the similarities with other experiences.

Moving along, its narrator recounts a story with a fair degree of melancholy and cynicism, something that is quite on the opposite side of the other narrator used as a comparison in *Stories: The Path of Destinies*. The differences in tone and focus are enough to make them two distinct experiences, with the former showing a lot of attention into keeping every element of a sentence in the context of a localization, and the latter demonstrating how to tackle difficult linguistic issues and English mannerisms through neutralizations or omissions. The same cannot be said for how *Biomutant* tackles wordplay, which can reach the point of love and care that a *Nintendo* game can show in its rich history. Standing right beside one another, *Biomutant* has shown that puns and composite words can be achieved greatly at the same level of games like the *Splatoon* series, with a type of Localization that can be cynic and playful at the same time. All of this is thanks to the onomatopoeias and sounds made by specific names and words that do show a species that is still in its infancy and does not understand everything the world has to offer.

When some things cannot be Localized, Transcreation comes to play. As was said above, Transcreation can help in the process of Adapting something that cannot sit quite right in another Localization. This has not changed in time, as Gabriele Vegetti states in our interview, although it is important to master this form of Adaptation as soon as possible in order to make it work as well as it can possibly do. Some examples listed and discussed in this thesis do show the two sides of the coin, so to speak: on the one hand, there are a plethora of great diatopic variations explored through Adaptations of accents that should get addressed in some ways and in other languages. On the other, there are cases of Neutralizations that simplify the Localization process, but can make some jokes not work the same way in regards of their intentions or definitions, like the example from *Medieval Resurrection*. This means that Transcreation is a tool that needs to be mastered and developed further in due time.

Getting back to the topic of this study, all of the games that have been discussed have really similar backgrounds: the further we go back in time, the simpler and more straightforward the work process was. Gabriele Vegetti gave a counter-proof that made us take a peek into the work schedule of a video game in 2003 and, despite its good qualities, it was still a 2-man job. Perhaps it did not even need more professionals working into it, but all of the studios that worked on more recent video games did work together in-house and were a bit higher in numbers, from 3 to 4 people at once on the same language, as estimates show. The work schedule has changed, although it has remained really similar to how it used to be before, although with a lot more support from softwares and the like.

Lastly, despite *Biomutant* not leaving a huge mark in the video game industry, it left something nonetheless. It left a unique type of Localization that shows love, care and attention, which should happen more often and should be studied even more than in this thesis. The future after *Biomutant* shows that this type of love and attention has become increasingly frequent in the media, but with some caveats and conditions. With AI being more and more likely of a companion for Game Localizers, it is more important than ever to keep human input, at last, in order to make every Localization look, sound and feel as distinctive as possible, while at the same time keeping the same degree of faithfulness Localizers always want to achieve.

Appendix

Interview with Gabriele Vegetti

The following interview has been translated from Italian to English by myself. It was originally taken via e-mail on the September 21, 2025.

1. How many people worked on the Italian localization of *Rayman 3: Hoodlum Havoc*? Was it a group effort, or something You worked on alone?

- For what concerns the localization I think I worked on it alone with the help of a proofreader. For the voice acting I collaborated with a recording study, the defunct *Studio Florian* from Bologna.

2. How did the translation process actually work? Did you use CAT softwares? Was it all on paper or digital documents?

- CAT Softwares did exist back then but they were not that common nor easy to use in these contexts. Excel files were much more preferred for video games.

3. Were you called in by contract specifically and only for *Rayman 3*?

- No. We worked for other games as well within *Ubisoft*.

4. Did you work on the localization of other games before *Rayman 3*? Do You remember interesting tidbits?

- Too many to recount. Before opening *Orange Studio* I worked for *CTO*, an Italian distributor that worked with major publishing companies like *Electronic Arts* and others. I particularly worked on *LucasArts* products, so from 1995 to 2000 I managed the Localization of many of their graphic adventures: *Monkey Island 3* and *4*, *Grim Fandango* and others, as well as all of the *Star Wars* games of that era. I then worked for many other *Ubisoft* games under *Orange Studios*, as well as with other publishers.

5. Did you have context of what you were localizing? Did you know what you were localizing and in what specific point of the story, or who was speaking?

- I do not remember much about this, unfortunately. There was some context, maybe some preparatory cutscenes. We could directly speak with the developers if we had doubts.

6. How much time did it take to complete the whole localization work, roughly?

- I have no idea. Times were strict in general, so I would say not more than 3 or 4 months from the beginning of localization to the end of the linguistic testing process.

7. Was there a glossary, rules or indications to respect on localizations of character names or places?

- Yes. Being an already existing and established franchise, we had to follow the same glossary that was used in previous games.

8. From which language did You translate the game? My impressions make me guess it started from French, is it true?

- Exactly. This I do remember! They started by sending us the English localization, but I felt it was not effective; I then asked to work on the original one (developers were French), which was way more fun. Being familiar with French, localizing jokes was way easier.

9. The character of André (the bad guy) has a marked French accent. Was it your choice?

- Unfortunately, I do not remember. Could have either been an indication from the client or a choice from us.

10. Given a character with a strong accent inflection, did you think about adding Italian variations (dialetti) in the dialogues?

- No. Foreign accents are ok, but diatopic variations in voice acting are absolutely not recommended, unless there is a precise reason (i.e. the character is actually Neapolitan or Sicilian in the original). Trying to transform accents or inflections (like Scottish) in Italian variations always had bad results and has not been done in a long time.

11. Back to the character of Murphy he is maybe the most different from his English counterpart, both in tone and jokes. Do You remember anecdotes related to some jokes? Was his localization directly from French?

- As already stated, the localization has been made starting from French. It is possible that the jokes and lines came from the French

version as is. I cannot verify it since I do not have the French script anymore.

12. Did You get the chance to talk with other *Rayman 3* localizers for other languages?

- Not that I recall.

13. Did You have the chance to meet the Italian voice actors in order to consult on the execution of dubbed lines?

- I was always in the recording studio when they were working on the game, so yes. Furthermore, I had known them for a long time because we worked on other video games together, so the exchange was always present and tight. (He sent a link here, it can be found in the “websites” section)

14. Were there limitations on how many characters could be used within a sentence?

- There usually are limitations on audio. Lines cannot be longer nor shorter than the original over a certain percentage. Cutscenes make use of lip-sync and sound-sync, so adaptations are needed. Limits from audio are directly reflected on the length of translated sentences.

15. How much freedom did you have in localizing lines and jokes?

- Total. There were no approval steps because the client trusted our work. The only important thing was to not get overboard with foul

language because this was a game for younger audiences, but these were self-imposed limits more than anything.

16. Did Orange Studio work on something else in the Game Localization field after *Rayman 3*, even with other developers? On what games?

- Yes, for many years. Once again, we worked on so many games in a year, so writing a list is impossible. Among the most important titles I remember many games from the *Splinter Cell* series from 2004 to 2010 with Luca Ward and Morgan, the first *Far Cry* game, *Rayman Raving Rabbids* and many others. I then closed *Orange Studio* in 2011 and then moved on to collaborate with *Native Prime sas*.

17. On a scale of importance, how much of an impact did Transcreation have compared to other localization techniques? Do you feel like Transcreation is more or less important than before?

- It was pretty important in this case in particular. It has the same degree of importance today, being more related to the product type. Of course, for video games that have a high degree of humour Transcreation is an important part, because adapting it to an Italian audience is essential. War games have usually way less to Transcreate when compared. It is also an ability that you learn with time. If I had to work today on the same graphic adventures I had to localize thirty years ago, my choices would be completely different.

18. How is the work for a Translator/Localizer today, both in regards of finding new projects and work difficulties? Was it easier or harder before?

- It was surely simpler even for a small reality like ours to get in touch with big publishers. The industry changed a lot today and I am very happy that someone else has to take care of business development! A lot has changed from an operational point of view as well. CAT Softwares made our jobs way easier, but publisher requests are even more urgent, development times are longer and localization times stricter. It is not that uncommon to work on projects that have more than a million worlds in just a few months, which forces people to work with different localization teams of translators and revisors simultaneously, with all the difficulties that come from it as a result.

19. There are some instances of characters saying very strong sentences (i.e. in *Rayman 3*, the King of the Knaaren, Gumsi, calls Rayman “aborto smembrato” – “dismembered abortion”, or André calls Globox “ritardato” – “retarded”). Do You remember these lines? How was the sentiment towards these in regards of translating them?

- There you go, these two examples would not be accepted at all today! They could go relatively unnoticed 20 years ago because linguistic and cultural sensitivities were way different, but this is something I would not do today.

20. What do you think will be the future of game localization, especially when the fast AI development is taken into account?

- This question is very hard to answer. We always have an eye on AI and LLM developments. Sometimes publishers ask us to use these tools to reduce times and costs, but at the same time we still try to maintain creative control on our work, so we always make sure that the last part of every work is verified by a “human” linguist before it

leaves our hands. Everything is still at the beginning, there is still the need to integrate, using the possibilities of the tool without leaving the last parts of the work to them.

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